

Intelligent Trust and Security Orchestration for 6G Distributed Cloud Environments

Deliverable 7.2

**Interim Report on Dissemination and
Exploitation of the Results and Interactions to
Standardisations**

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15995199](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15995199)

Contractual Date of Delivery:	April 30, 2025
Actual Date of Delivery:	May 15, 2025
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Work Package	WP7
Target Dissemination Level	Public

*This work is supported by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139198, **iTrust6G** project. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or SNS-JU. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*

Revision History

Revision	Date	Editor / Commentator	Description of Edits
0.1	2024-03-23	Antonio Lioy (POLITO)	Template and ToC made ready
0.2	2025-04-04	Sheeba, Souvik (Lenovo)	One round of review completed, added refinement and suggestions. Also provided input to Clause 6.
0.3	2025-04-07	Luís Landeiro Ribeiro (PDMFC)	Exploitation improvements
0.4	2025-04-07	Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)	Communications and External Liaison Sections
0.5	2025-04-10	Antonio Lioy (POLITO) Souvik (Lenovo)	Version for internal review Individual exploitation plans
0.6	2025-04-23	Souvik (Lenovo)	Updated Table 5 on KER
0.7	2025-04-23	Sheeba (Lenovo)	Final review completed – Added refinements and suggestions where fixes are needed.
0.8	2025-04-29	Luís Landeiro Ribeiro (PDMFC)	Extend description of business canvas
0.9	2025-05-12	Rhys Miller (GIGASYS)	Full review and style adjustment
1.0	2025-05-15	Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)	Final proof reading and submission

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth Generation of Mobile Communications
6G	Sixth Generation of Mobile Communications
AI	Artificial Intelligence
B5G	Beyond Fifth Generation Mobile Communications
CA	Consortium Agreement
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DoA	Description of Action
HWP	Horizontal Working Party
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
IT	Information Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
MDP	Multi-domain Data-Plane
OT	Operational Technology
PoC	Proof of Concept
PPPs	Public-private partnerships
QA	Quality Assurance
SDO	Standardisation Development Organisation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Systems Joint Undertaking
TB	Technology Board
TMV	Test, Measurement, and KPIs Validation
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication
WG	Work Group
WP	Work Package
ZTA	Zero-Trust Architecture

Executive Summary

This document represents the iTrust6G D7.2 “Interim Report on Dissemination and Exploitation of the Results and Interactions to Standardisations”, envisaged in the framework of iTrust6G Work Package 7 (WP7) to report about the activities performed in the first 16 months of the project.

To this end, iTrust6G D7.2 contains the achieved results as well as an update of the initial plan for the rest of the project’s lifetime. Here is a brief description of what is reported:

- Regarding the general communications and project tools, it is explained that the project tools made available from the start of the project, and means for general communications, i.e., project website and social media accounts have been active from the start and are kept active according to the plan all through the reporting period in the document. Project’s internal communications, i.e., WP specific and plenary meetings were performed according to the schedule.
- On dissemination activities, project has made 7 scientific publications already. This number is expected to increase significantly during the remaining 14 months of the project as the project results are just started to appear. On invited talks and events there has been 5 of talks in various events so far. In addition, iTrust6G has organised 2 major workshops, and one industrial event is planned to be held in June 2025.
- On contribution to standardisation activities, the project has made 113 contributions so far, which is a truly outstanding figure, and 2 open-source contribution was made, while more contributions are expected in the coming months.
- Regarding the liaison with SNS community, iTrust6G has been one of the most active SNS projects with 100% participation in board meetings, and participation in majority of working groups, and project contributions appeared in 6 SNS/6GIA white papers.
- In terms of exploitation of the project results, the innovation manager has been working with the consortium to formulate and facilitate the identification of projects key exploitation results, innovation assets, and exploitation target groups; providing support and mentorship on IPR management, market analysis, and business models and canvas; and refining individual and joint exploitation plans.

All in all, iTrust6G D7.2 reflects the project’s strength on issues such as standardisation contributions and dissemination and communication activities and provides insights on activities that can be improved during the second half of the project, such as presence in social media, and participation in industrial events. The report also documents the plans and guidelines for exploitation of the project’s results by consortium partners that will be followed during the rest of the project and after its end.

A final report on dissemination, communication, standardisation contributions, and exploitation activities will be delivered at the end of the project (month 30): iTrust6G D7.3, “Final Report on Dissemination, Impact and Exploitation of the Results”.

1 Introduction

This document, iTrust6G D7.2, presents the project results in WP7 at M16 concerning dissemination, communication, standardisation, and exploitation actions. It corresponds to the Milestone MS13 “iTrust6G consortium intermediate exploitation and dissemination”. All milestones and deliverables related to WP7 activities are shown in Figure 1-1.

Figure 1-1 iTrust6G dissemination, communication, and exploitation related milestones and deliverables

This document is organized in eight sections:

- Section 1 contains a general introduction;
- Section 2 summarizes the target audience and reports the expected KPIs, along with the values achieved at M16;
- Section 3 describes the achieved results for communication, along with an update of the communication plan of the project;
- Section 4 describes the achieved results for dissemination, along with an update of the dissemination plan of the project;
- Section 5 describes the actions performed for liaison with external organisations, specifically SNS JU and 6GIA, and reports about future activities;
- Section 6 describes the achieved results for standardisation, along with an update of the standardisation plan of the project;
- Section 7 provides an update of the individual and joint exploitation plans, along with the results achieved so far;
- Section 8 concludes the document and provides pointers to upcoming work on these topics.

2 Communication and Dissemination Target Audience and KPIs

The communication and dissemination activities have been targeted at the audience fully described in Table 2-1 of iTrust6G D7.1 [1] and briefly summarized here for ease of reference.

- Industry Verticals
- Vendors and Service Providers
- Network Operators
- Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)
- Open-Source Communities
- Standard Developing Organizations (SDOs)
- Academia and Research Centres
- General Public

The impact of the iTrust6G dissemination and communication activities will be regularly assessed through Key Performance Indicator (KPI) monitoring. Table 2-11 summarizes the KPIs of the project's communication and dissemination based on description of action (DoA), along with the values achieved at M16.

Table 2-1 iTrust6G Dissemination KPIs

Activity	Description	KPI	KPI value at M16
Website	Making information on project available to the public, including objectives, publications, media, etc. https://www.sns-iTrust6G.com/	2000 unique visitors per year	1800 hits
Workshops, Events	Participation in Innovation Events and Workshops in European cities so that the project's concept and results are spread.	Audience of 50-100 per event, 20-70 per workshop	2 workshops planned
Industrial Exhibitions	Industrial exhibitions demonstrating how the tools under development can assist the industrial sector.	1 exhibition per year that will demonstrate the progress towards achieving the project's goals	1 industrial exhibition planned
Publications	Papers submitted to scientific journals, conferences, or workshops	> 25 papers (at least 5 of them with an impact factor at least 2) > 10 conferences	1 journal 5 conference papers
Participation in 5G/Beyond Fifth Generation (B5G) initiatives	Members of the consortium will attend 5G initiatives to be informed about technological progress affecting the project's objectives	At least 2 initiatives per year will be attended	>20
Social Networks	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives and results	At least 1 weekly update on Twitter 600 followers on LinkedIn	157 followers on the LinkedIn; More than one post per week in LinkedIn
Articles, Press Releases, etc.	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives, and results	At least 10 articles and press releases during the project	2 newsletters

Open-Source Datasets Published	At least 2 databases will be published in the project lifetime with publicly accessible knowledge from the project's results.	1 open access database on threat modelling and classification	0
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3 Communication Activities

To carry out the project tasks and activities, and achieve its technical and dissemination targets and objectives, all partners in the iTrust6G consortium will be actively involved in:

- Internal communication channels, i.e., project email lists and repository;
- External communication channels, i.e., project website;
- Project's social media.

This section provides a detailed insight into the tools used for these channels.

3.1 Internal communication tools

As the most important tool for the project execution, the project collaboration tool (Microsoft Teams) has been running from the start of the project, and all active WP activities, including WP calls have been running from M02. Among the processes and procedures to keep the project activities running according to the plan and to keep track of everything, the following can be mentioned:

- Project's members list, including the responsibilities and contact details,
- Project Gantt, list of deliverables and milestones, updated continuously,
- Project KPIs tracking sheet, including details such as relevant WPs and associated Proof of Concepts (PoCs) (or any evaluations methods), status of the works towards achieving the KPI, and any identified risks,
- Project Action Points tracking sheet, to note and follow any APs decided in plenary meetings. Each WP has its own specific meeting minutes and APs folder and documents,
- Project risk tracking sheet, to keep the list of all identified risks and methods to mitigate or deal with the risks according to the project handbook,
- Project templates kept in a dedicated folder,
- Project timeline to collectively show the timelines of the project activities and important deadlines,
- The information of project's liaison with SNS and 6GIA, and any other external organisation, are kept in a dedicated folder.

3.2 Project meetings

As explained in the introduction, the main interactions to perform the technical activities of the project in the framework of WPs are fortnightly calls per WP. In addition, to evaluate the overall progress and status of the project, and to steer the next activities of the project toward targets, the project organizes 3 plenaries per year.

Table 3-1 shows the project meetings plan and those held so far. There have been 4 plenary meetings so far. The kick-off meeting was held in January 2024, soon after the project was started. The first 3 plenary meetings were held in two full days format, whereas for the 4th plenary meeting the project management team foresaw more time required for the discussions and therefore the 4th plenary meeting was held in 3 days. Project plenary meetings are structured in slot for specific technical topic discussions, and each WP has a dedicated slot to discuss the status and next plans for each WP and task. The meeting slots are filled with technical discussions, status report and project plannings. The next (5th) plenary is planned and is going to be held in POLITO premises in Turin, Italy, on 28 and 29 of May. All other future plenaries will be planned gradually.

Table 3-1 iTrust6G Plenary Meetings, Review Meetings, and Final Demo Plans

No	Title	Date	Format	Venue	Host	Status
1	Kick Off	2024-01 25-26	F2F	Barcelona, Spain	i2CAT	Done
2	2nd Plenary	2024-05 30-31	F2F	Crete, Greece	ADR	Done
3	3rd Plenary	2024-09 25-26	F2F	Athens, Greece	NTUA	Done
4	4th Plenary	2025-01 22-24	F2F	Lisbon, Portugal	PDM	Done
5	Project Interim Review I	2025-03 11	Remote	MS Teams	PC	Planned
6	5th Plenary	2025-05 28-29	F2F	Turin, Italy	POLITO	in planning
7	6th Plenary	2025-09-??	F2F	TBC	LEN	TBC
8	7th Plenary	2026-01-??	F2F	TBC	GIGASYS	TBC
9	8th Plenary / WS?	2026-03-??	F2F	TBC	TBC	TBC
10	Final Demonstrations	2026-06-??	F2F	TBC	TID UC3M	TBC
11	Project Final Review	2026-06-??	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC

3.3 Project external communications

3.3.1 Project Website

iTrust6G hosts a comprehensive, regularly updated, public website. It contains all relevant project information such as the global vision and objectives, its relation to 6GIA, SNS JU and other projects in the same domain, and the iTrust6G consortium. The site provides access to the public deliverables of iTrust6G, as well as publications, and public materials, such as flyers, posters, and other collateral. The site news channel provides an overview of iTrust6G events and other relevant events. A database, under General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines, has been built and now it has two blog posts uploaded with another due next quarter. All relevant news posted to LinkedIn and X also gets posted to the ‘news’ section of the iTrust6G site. The website's electronic address is, www.sns-iTrust6G.com and the main page is presented in Figure 3-1.

To ease accessibility, the website content has been split in the following sections:

- **Home** is the main page of iTrust6G website, which enables easier browsing of the website content. It also contains links to social media channels.
- **Project**, contains an overall description of this project, presenting the iTrust6G vision, concept, innovation, and demonstrators.
- **News**, relevant news and blog posts about iTrust6G activities and results, which will also be posted on iTrust6G social media channels to increase project’s visibility.
- **Deliverables**, publishes project’s submitted public deliverables.
- **Disseminations**, contains all disseminations including publications, talks and events, open-source contributions as well as the project’s contributions to the standardisation activities.
- **Consortium** introduces iTrust6G project partners.
- **Contact** contains a contact form to provide a contact channel for all relevant communications to the iTrust6G consortium, and introduces project coordinator, project manager, and technical coordinator.

Figure 3-2 shows the status of the iTrust6G website’s unique hits during mid-December 2024 to Mid-January 2025 period. The website hits vary between few hits a day up to 20 hits (this is the case for other months as well), that means around 100 to 200 hits per month.

Figure 3-1 iTrust6G website: screenshot of the main page

Figure 3-2 Status of Website Hits during December 2024 - January 2025

3.3.2 Project social media

LinkedIn has established itself as a business and employment-oriented social network. Since LinkedIn is tailored for professionals, it is well suited to communicate the activities and contributions carried out in iTrust6G project. To that end, iTrust6G project management has created a project specific page¹ whose main purpose is to reach out to iTrust6G target audience, especially professionals, researchers and academics. The LinkedIn page intends to foster discussions on relevant aspects of the project, advertise news and events, and collect stakeholder’ opinions. Figure 3-3 shows a screenshot of the LinkedIn page.

¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/sns-iTrust6G-project-1342a92a8/>

iTrust6G has been building a steady following on LinkedIn and X, posting at least twice a week. Content ranges from upcoming plenary information and workshop attendance to videos and graphics encouraging followers to visit the iTrust6G website. Posts on LinkedIn get an average of 12 likes per post, with 2 shares and 1 comment.

On X, we are still working on building the number of followers therefore the likes are slightly lower, but it is still an effective platform to interact with other projects on and post shorter form of content. LinkedIn is the best performing social channel for the project, and iTrust6G best performing posts are often video based.

iTrust6G has promoted its first newsletter (published in December 2024) via LinkedIn and X and uses both platforms to interact with other projects and partners.

iTrust6G LinkedIn page has 60 connections and 121 followers as of March 2025. The average post on the page has been 2 posts per week.

3.3.3 YouTube channel

YouTube is the most popular video-sharing platform in the world. Thus, it is the perfect social channel to broadcast the main activities carried out in the project. For that reason, iTrust6G hosts a YouTube channel that provides video content produced by the project to stakeholders at this address (<https://www.youtube.com/@SNSiTrust6G>). Figure 3-4 shows iTrust6G YouTube channel.

Figure 3-3 The screenshot of iTrust6G LinkedIn page

Figure 3-4 iTrust6G YouTube Channel

4 Dissemination Activities

The general dissemination strategy of iTrust6G is to present results at conferences, workshops, panels, forums, and their technical Working Group (WG) meetings, industrial forums, and other events on a European and International scale, aiming both at public and private sectors. This will be supported by publications in international scientific journals (targeting an expert audience) and in scientific magazines (aimed to a broader audience).

4.1 Scientific publications

Currently the project's partners have published or submitted the following papers related to the concepts of iTrust6G project:

- 1) Afroditi Blika, Stefanos Pamos, George Doukas, Vangelis Lamprou, Sotiris Pelekis, Michael Kontoulis, Christos Ntanos, Dimitrios Askounis, "Federated Learning for Enhanced Cybersecurity and Trustworthiness In 5G and 6G Networks: A Comprehensive Survey", IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society, DOI: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2024.3449563
- 2) E. Bravi, A. Lioy, D. Berbecaru, "Integrity Management in Softwarized Networks", IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium, Seoul (South Korea), May 6–10, 2024, DOI: 10.1109/NOMS59830.2024.10574994
- 3) S. Pelekis, E. Karakolis, G. Lampropoulos, S. Mouzakitis, O. Markaki, C. Ntanos, D. Askounis, "Trustworthy artificial intelligence in the energy sector: Landscape analysis and evaluation framework", ICE: International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation, Funchal – Madeira (Portugal), June 24 – 28, 2024.
- 4) F. Settanni, A. Zamponi, C. Basile, "Dynamic Security Provisioning for Cloud-Native Networks: An Intent-Based Approach", IEEE CSR: International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience, London (United Kingdom), September 2–4, 2024.
- 5) M. Asad, M. Compastie, M. S. Siddiqui, V. Daza, "Extending Orchestration for Privacy Preservation in Beyond 5G and 6G Networks", FNWF 2024: IEEE Future Networks World Forum, Dubai (UAE), October 15–17, 2024.
- 6) M. Ghoraishi, M. S. Siddiqui, M. Compastie, S. Mhiri, C. Ntanos, M. Kontoulis, D. Lopez, A. Lioy, E. K. Markakis, S. Backia Mary Baskaran, "iTrust6G: Zero-Trust Security for 6G Networks", FNWF 2024: IEEE Future Networks World Forum, Dubai (UAE), October 15–17, 2024.
- 7) S. Pelekis, T. Koutroubas, A. Blika, E. Karakolis, C. Ntanos, D. Askounis, "Adversarial Machine Learning in Electrical Energy and Power System: a Survey", 23rd International Conference on e-Society, Funchal – Madeira (Portugal), March 1-3, 2025.
- 8) S. Paul, S.B.M Baskaran, A Kunz, A. Salkintzis, "Evolution of Policy Verification and Control for 6G Secure Service Orchestration in Telco Clouds", 2025 EuCNC & 6G Summit – NET, Poznan (Poland), June 3–6, 2025 (accepted).
- 9) Sotiris Pelekis, Thanos Koutroubas, Afroditi Blika, Anastasis Berdelis, Evangelos Karakolis, Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Askounis, "Adversarial machine learning: A review of methods, tools, and critical industry domains", Artificial Intelligence Review (accepted).
- 10) Vangelis Lamprou, George Doukas, Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Askounis, "On the Trustworthiness of Federated Learning Models for 5G - Network Intrusion Detection under Heterogeneous Data", Computer Networks (under review).

- 11) Loukas Ilias, George Doukas, Vangelis Lamprou, Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Askounis, “Convolutional Neural Networks and Mixture of Experts for Intrusion Detection in 5G Networks and beyond”, Information Fusion (under review).

All partners – but especially the research and academic ones – will continue their efforts to publish the project’s results in scientific venues, that is major journals and magazines, e.g. by IEEE, ACM, Springer, Elsevier, so on, and international conferences.

4.2 Talks and events

iTrust6G has been involved in several workshops and talks, including:

- ***iTrust6G Project Introduction (SNS Webinar), March 7, 2024.***
by Coordinator, Mir Ghoraishi
Available on YouTube:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VIsMwxEUGD8&pp=ygURaXRydXN0NmCGY2hhbm5lbCA%3D>
- ***iTrust6G Introduction Poster, EUCNC’2024, June 2024.***
by Mir Ghoraishi (Coordinator), and Maxime Compastie (i2CAT), who presented the iTrust6G introduction in the EUCNC’2024 poster booth.
- ***iTrust6G – Project Scope and Ambitions, in 6G Platform Germany Trustworthiness Working Group Meeting, June 24, 2024.***
By Coordinator, Mir Ghoraishi
Project scope and ambitions were presented to 6G Platform Germany, Trustworthiness Working Group, online meeting.
- ***Introducing the Project and the Proposed Architecture, in IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF), October 2024.***
The coordinator, Dr Mir Ghoraishi, and technical manager, Dr Shuaib Seddiqui, presented iTrust6G in two presentations at the IEEE FNWF 2024 conference. First was ‘Zero-Trust Security for 6G Networks’ and the second was ‘Extending Orchestration for Privacy Preservation in Beyond 5G and 6G Networks’. Mir also spoke in ‘Symposium on Optical-Wireless Convergence: Beyond Xhaul, enabling the communications-computing continuum’.
- ***IEEE International Workshop on Computer Aided Modelling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD) 2024***
Shuaib Seddiqui attended the IEEE International Workshop on ‘Computer Aided Modelling and Design of Communication Links and Networks’ (CAMAD), October 2024. He presented iTrust6G objectives and architecture and discussed ‘AI Enabled Collaborative Threat Intelligence’.
- ***IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium***
E. Bravi presented iTrust6G’s work at the IEEE NOMS 2024 conference where integrity attestation of distributed infrastructures (cloud, SDN, NFV) was discussed.

4.3 Organisation of workshops and panel discussions

As of reporting this iTrust6G D7.2, the project has organized two workshops that will take place in the first half of 2025.

4.3.1 SecSoft Workshop

The SecSoft-2025 workshop is part of the IEEE NetSoft conference <https://netsoft2025.ieee-netsoft.org/> which is focused on software networking and will take place in Budapest (Hungary) on June 23-27, 2025. SecSoft will be focused on the security aspects of software networks and is jointly organized with other projects in the spirit of international collaboration.

The workshop URI is <https://www.secsoft-workshop.org/> and this is the header of the home page of the workshop:

Figure 4-1 SecSoft Workshop

4.3.2 EUCNC 2025 Workshop and Expert Panel on 6G Trustworthiness

Additionally, iTrust6G is the lead organiser of the workshop titled “6G Trustworthiness: Requirements, Challenges, and Considerations” as part of the EuCNC & 6G Summit, taking place on June 3rd, 2025, in Poznań (Poland). The workshop is contributed by ten SNS projects, being MARE, NETWORK, HORSE, PRIVATEER, RIGOROUS, HORSE, Safe-6G, VERG, ROBUST6G, CONFIDENTIAL6G, in collaboration with the 6G Platform Germany and co-organized by the 6G-IA Security Working Group. It will feature representatives from these projects sharing their insights, achievements, lessons learned, and the latest developments from the SNS JU initiative. More information is available in EUCNC and 6G Summit website².

In addition, the workshop program also includes an expert panel discussion where Dr Mir Ghoraihi, iTrust6G coordinator is the moderator, and Dr Shuaib Siddiqui, iTrust6G technical manager is among experts.

4.3.3 EUCNC 2025 Exhibition Booth

iTrust6G has co-organised a joint booth titled “Distributed Trustworthiness and Security Analytics for 6G Systems”, shared with the ROBUST6G and PRIVATEER projects. The booth will feature five demonstrations, including two presented by iTrust6G:

² <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/workshops/workshop-6/>

- **Policy-Based Trust Evaluation Across Network Services in Multi-Domain Environments**
This demo illustrates how trust policies are used to evaluate multiple network services deployed across various administrative domains.
- **Risk-Aware and CTI-Enabled Attack Remediation in Multi-Domain Environments**
This demonstration focuses on collaborative security among multiple stakeholders to ensure the network remains in a trustworthy state.

4.4 Industrial exhibitions

iTrust6G, in collaboration with Thales SIX GTS, is organizing an industrial workshop and exhibition in Paris on June 17, 2025. During the event, the iTrust6G project will present key developments in its trust and security architecture along with following topics:

- Instrumenting TOSCA for holistic security orchestration
- Remote attestation for trustworthy networks
- Policy-based mechanisms for secure connectivity
- Secure service orchestration through policy verification

The workshop will also feature two new demonstrations from iTrust6G:

- Risk-Aware and CTI-Enabled Attack Remediation in Multi-Domain Environments
- Policy-Based Trust Evaluation Across Network Services in Multi-Domain Environments

These demonstrations highlight cutting-edge approaches that the iTrust6G project is undertaken and display the progress of the project.

4.5 Newsletters

iTrust6G has already published 2 newsletters which was sent out to the community email lists and shared on LinkedIn and X on December 24th, 2024, and May 2025.

These newsletters covered the general and technical news and events related to the project, plus short description of the achieved technical works. The newsletters also covered some general information, such as project use cases, plenary meetings, deliverables and links to iTrust6G publications.

4.6 Open-source contributions

To benefit from the Open-Source Communities the iTrust6G project will establish active participation in the OSM community.

In addition, as part of “Open-Source Datasets Published” activity, as reported in iTrust6 D7.1 [1], at least 2 databases will be published through the project duration that will contain publicly accessible database knowledge from the project’s results. In several tasks of WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6 part of the anticipated outputs will be Artificial Intelligence (AI) models and generated datasets. The AI models will be trained on both open-source and iTrust6G datasets and will be used for detection and enrichment of data. Those models will be uploaded to appropriate online open-source repositories (e.g. Hugging face). Regarding the generated datasets, related to captured traffic internally in iTrust6G project or generated for the execution of the use cases in testbeds, will be also released either through related publications or shared on open-source repositories. Below in Table 4-1 the contributions to open-source are detailed:

Table 4-1 Contribution to Open-Source

#	Partners	Open-Source Contribution/ Participation Topics	Community Project	Related WP	Achievement Status (e.g., Contribution(s) Information)
1	TID	Proposal for OSM long-term view in connection with research projects: https://docbox.etsi.org/OSG/OSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2023/OSM(23)000057_OSM_Long_Term_View__Telef_nica_.pptx	OSM	WP7	Contributed. Under discussion in OSM Technical Steering Committee.
2	PDM	Improved the Chimera Golang agent to collect metrics. Code to be released under MIT license already published to GitHub but still in private repo while internal company approvals go through legal.	Chimera	WP3 WP5	Contributed date time auto detection from unstructured logs. Support for Cryptographic digital signatures for batches of events to ensure integrity. Added support for Fortigate log format and CheckPoint CEF format. Contributed Redis sink and source integration. Added custom parser for Key-Value parses with improved performance. Initial support for eBPF.

5 Liaison with External Organisations

5.1 Liaison with SNS and 6GIA

To satisfy the contractual commitments in the collaboration agreement, **iTrust6G** has been active in participation in the community events, joint reporting and dissemination, and other sorts of interactions. The project became active as soon as it was kicked off in January 2024.

A summary of **iTrust6G** liaison with SNS and 6GIA in the first 12 months of the project are as:

- 100% participation in Steering Board, and Technical Board meetings, surveys and questionnaires,
- 100% attendance in SNS JU Communication meetings,
- Participation in all relevant Working Groups and related activities according to the Table 3-2,
- Contribution to and participation in the editorial team of Architecture WG White Paper,
- Contribution to SNS TB AI White Paper,
- Contribution to Security WG White Paper,
- Contribution to Technology Board (TB) AI/ Machine Learning (ML) White Paper,
- Contribution to TMV KPI and KVI White Papers.

Table 5-1 iTrust6G Delegates in SNS, 6GIA, and Network Europe WGs

SNS WG	iTrust6G Delegate Name	Partner
Steering Board	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
	Khash Rahimi	GIGASYS
Technical Board	Shuaib Siddiqi	I2CAT
	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
Architecture WG	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
	Saber Mhrir & Shuaib Siddiqi	I2CAT
	Christos Nanos, George Doukas	NTUA
	Diego Lopez	TID
TMV WG	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
Reliable Software Network WG	Souvik Paul	LENOVO
6GIA Security WG	Shuaib Siddiqi; Maxime Compastié	I2CAT
	Evangelos Markakis	ADR
	Diego Lopez	TID
	Rhys Miller	GIGASYS
6GIA Pre-Standardisation WG	Apostolis Salkintzis	LENOVO
	Diego Lopez	TID
	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
6GIA Trials WG	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
6GIA Vision WG	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
6GIA Open SNS WG	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS
Network Europe SME WG	Mir Ghoraishi	GIGASYS

5.2 Liaison with other external organisations

In addition to the collaborations within SNS community, **iTrust6G** is taking any opportunity to collaborate and liaise with related activities in Europe. In this regard, the following interactions were initiated in the first period of the project:

- Interactions with 6G Platform Germany: iTrust6G Coordinator reached out to 6G Platform Germany, Trustworthiness WG, and the project were introduced. This followed by an invited presentation on the Introduction of iTrust6G in 6G Platform Germany, Trustworthiness WG in June 2024. Further, 6G Platform Germany, Trustworthiness WG, is invited to participate in the workshop on trustworthiness, organised, and proposed by the iTrust6G Coordinator for EUCNC 2025. In addition, iTrust6G is invited to participate to the workshop that will be organised by 6G Platform Germany, around July 2025.
- Interactions with Thales SIX GTS: iTrust6G has been in discussion with Thales SIX GTS France, on organising a workshop where project, iTrust6G plans, innovations, and solutions that will be presented to Thales experts for further scientific and technical exchanges. This is ongoing and the workshop will be held on June 17, 2025, in Thales premises in Paris, France, where a delegate from iTrust6G will participate to present and demonstrate project solutions.

6 Standardisation Activities

For the iTrust6G project, prioritizing and engaging with the most pertinent standardization areas is essential to achieving its goals. The project focuses on several key standardization domains:

- **Security architectures and protocols:** Contributing to shaping the security architectures and protocols for future 6G networks. This effort aims to ensure that the project's security solutions and trust mechanisms are in line with current industry standards and best practices.
- **Network slicing and orchestration:** The project is involved in the standardization process for network slicing and orchestration methods. This participation ensures that iTrust6G's advancements in secure service orchestration remain compatible with the evolving standards of the industry.
- **Trust management and algorithms:** Influencing the standardization of trust management frameworks and algorithms. This includes promoting the project's innovative trust management strategies and the integration of AI-based solutions.
- **Security requirements and best practices:** By collaborating with standardization bodies, iTrust6G aims to help define the security requirements and best practices for 6G networks. This collaboration will incorporate the project's research outcomes and technological innovations.
- **Open interfaces and interoperability:** The project is engaged in standardization activities concerning open interfaces and the interoperability of 6G networks. This ensures that iTrust6G security solutions are designed for easy integration with various systems and technologies.

The iTrust6G consortium has targeted several standardization bodies, and groups within them, contributing project results to their work items. Table 6-1 shows the list reports the activities performed until M16.

Table 6-1 iTrust6G Target Standardisation Bodies and Working Groups

No	Partners	Standardization Efforts/ Participation Topics	SDO	WP	Date	Achievement Status (e.g., Contribution(s) Information)
1	LEN	Zero Trust Security: Security study scope for the following: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data exposure for security evaluation and monitoring. 2. Security mechanism for dynamic policy enforcement 	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4	26 Feb - 01 March, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-240897
2	LEN	Zero Trust Security: Security Assumptions were defined to be used as building blocks for the standards solution. The Security function that performs the security evaluation and monitoring resides in the operator's domain (i.e., external to the 3GPP network) and it is considered as a trusted entity. This Security function and its application logic are up to the operator's implementation, and it	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4	26 Feb - 01 March, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-240898 • S3-240902

		can be outside the scope of 3GPP. The dynamic security policy enforcement is configured and controlled by the operator based on operator's policy.				
3	LEN	Security evaluation and monitoring inputs: Data Collection on SBA layer i.e., Malformed messages (i.e., SBI message violations) may be received by a NF over an SBI from another NF (e.g., due to malicious intentions or due to mere error). The malformed message(s) sent with malicious intentions have the potential to cause failure/malfunction of NF(s).	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	26 Feb - 01 March, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Data related to Malformed Message: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-240903
4	LEN	Security evaluation and monitoring inputs: Data Collection on SBA layer. i.e., A core SBA NF that receives a massive number of service API invocations that intends to exhaust the network resource may lead to degradation or complete shutdown of NF thus resulting in a Denial of Service (DoS).	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	26 Feb - 01 March, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Data related to massive number of Service Messages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-240904
5	LEN	The need for Security evaluation and monitoring in SBA: Potential Security threats in SBA. i.e., If any NF that has been deployed in the core network, becomes compromised or starts to behave maliciously, and remain undetected then the NF could be misused in attacks leading to a service failure, data loss/theft, etc.	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	26 Feb - 01 March, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Key Issue#1 on Data exposure for security evaluation and monitoring: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241005
6	LEN	Security evaluation and monitoring results based improved access control: Potential SBA authorization and access control scenarios. i.e., Security Request Process, NF Service Registration update, and NF Service Discovery.	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	26 Feb - 01 March, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Use case for

						security policy enforcement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241021
7	LEN	Key Issue on dynamic policy enforcement: Potential threats in SBA access control. i.e., the NRF if not updated with information about an NF that has been subject to an attack and mitigations are only performed at infrastructure layers, an attacker could reuse information gained during the attack for extending or renewing the attack.	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	15-19 April, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Adding Key Issue on WT2 "Security mechanism for dynamic policy enforcement": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241526
8	LEN	The need for Security evaluation and monitoring in SBA: Potential Security Requirements. i.e., The 5GS should provide the means to facilitate collection of data potentially relevant for operator-based security evaluation and monitoring.	3GPP SA3 WG	WP5	15 - 19 April, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Adding requirements to KI#1 "Data exposure for security evaluation and monitoring": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241525
9	LEN	Security evaluation and monitoring results based improved access control: Clarification of malicious NF. i.e., if the security evaluation and monitoring results identifies an attack being performed by an NF, then that NF cannot be allowed to continue to consume or provide services to the rest of the NFs. A compromised NF can increase the threat/attack surface, impact other NFs, and affect the overall service availability.	3GPP SA3 WG	WP3 WP5	15 – 19 April, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Updates to Access control decision enhancement use case: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241137
10	LEN	Potential Massive number of SBI messages data to be collected: Evaluation of the identified potential data. i.e., Based on Operator policy the deviations from the normal behaviour can be	3GPP SA3 WG	WP3 WP5	15 – 19 April, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on

		<p>identified using any one or more of the following methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -One or more NF are sending more requests than their historic normal amount. -Victim NF(s) begins to respond with 500 Server Error Response HTTP Status Codes. -Victim NF(s) performance begins to drop. -The increased traffic does not adhere to historically normal traffic flows. -Standardized services by NRF and OAM in TS 23.288 for NF load (clause 6.5) and network performance (clause 6.6) analytics. If deployed, such services can be also used additionally. -On the SBA layer, there are standardized means to enforce a limit on the number of incoming requests via the HTTP2 SETTINGS_MAX_CONCURRENT_STREAMS parameter as described in RFC 9113. Based on operator policy, if such limit is set and if any requests exceed the limit, such event information can also be used. 				<p>enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Updates to Massive number of SBI messages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241568
11	LEN	<p>Potential Malformed messages received data to be collected: Evaluation of the identified potential data. i.e., Based on Operator’s policy, malformed message related event data (e.g., the NF identification information and the malformed message event information) can be logged for security evaluation and monitoring purposes. If such logs are available, it is notified to the Operator’s Security Function to enable necessary security evaluation and monitoring to aid in timely threat detection.</p>	3GPP SA3 WG	WP3 WP5	15 – 19 April, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Updates to Malformed Message Use case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-241570

12	LEN	<p>Data Collection and exposure for security evaluation and monitoring: Indirect Data collection by Operator Security Function such as SIEM, SOAR via a data collection Function/NWDAF. i.e., According to operator policy, NWDAF subscribes to NF or OAM (i.e., Data Producer) for event exposure services related to the following security events (identified with suitable event IDs).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Authentication and Authorization failure event -Reconnaissance detected authentication and authorization event -Malformed SBI message event -Message and service load event -Abnormal SBI call flow event 	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	20-24 May, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Solution to KI#1 Network assisted data collection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-242424
13	LEN	<p>Data Collection and exposure for security evaluation and monitoring: Direct data collection by Operator Security Function such as SIEM, SOAR. i.e., The NF(s) based on operator policy can determine to collect security event(s) specific data (i.e, just configured to send security events under specific conditions) to enable Operator's security function-based security evaluation and monitoring.</p>	3GPP SA3 WG	WP4 WP5	20-24 May, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Solution to KI#1_Direct data collection:</p> <p>S3-242425</p>
14	LEN	<p>Key Issue on dynamic policy enforcement: Potential Security Requirement. i.e., The 5GS should provide the means to configure suitable PEP within the 5G SBA with information about an NF that has been subject to an attack.</p>	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	20-24 May, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Updates to eZTS Key Issue 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-242423
15	LEN	<p>Conclusion of security evaluation and monitoring: List of data collection scenarios. i.e., The</p>	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	19-23 Aug, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19</p>

		<p>security incidents or scenarios in SBA where data can be collected in the SBA layer includes</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1)authentication and authorization failure event; 2)unexpected setup of TLS session and API invocation related to unauthorized reconnaissance; 3)malformed message event; 4)high service load; 5)unexpected SBI call flows; and 6) unexpected use of APIs exposed by services in SBA layer 				<p>for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Initial Conclusion to KI#1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-243505
16	LEN	<p>Security Policy enforcement in SBA: Solution details. i.e., Following the security evaluation and monitoring process if an attack/security threat is identified about NF(s), the OSF based on operator policy notifies the designated 3GPP function, the security data containing per NF level attack/threat alert.</p> <p>Where the 3GPP function can be PCF or suitable existing NF to collect the security data and provide the related Operator’s security policies with recommended actions to the appropriate consumers (i.e., enforcement points) in the network. The Operator’s security policies that map security data to the recommended actions can be upto Operator’s implementation. The interface between OSF and 3GPP NF can be protected for integrity, replay, and confidentiality using TLS</p>	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	19-23 Aug, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Solution to KI#2 (Security Policy enforcement in SBA):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-243611
17	LEN	<p>Data Collection and exposure for security evaluation and monitoring: Solution evaluation. The network function level impacts were evaluated and listed per solution.</p>	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	19-23 Aug, 2024	<p>Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust</p>

						Security) - Updates to Solution #2: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-243496
18	LEN	Direct data collection by Operator Security Function such as SIEM, SOAR: Solution evaluation. The network function level impacts were evaluated and listed per solution.	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	19-23 Aug, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Updates to Solution#1: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-243497
19	LEN	Conclusion of security evaluation and monitoring: Requirements for security evaluation and monitoring. The key issue will be addressed by requirements for data collection to enable security evaluation and monitoring on the SBA layer. No new interface nor protocol will be specified as result of the work in this report.	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	14-18 Oct, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - eZTS KI 1 Conclusions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-244327
20	LEN	Conclusion of dynamic policy enforcement: Reusing existing mechanisms for dynamic access control in SBA. i.e., No normative work is needed for KI#2.	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	14-18 Oct, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - Conclusion for Key Issue #2 "Security mechanisms for policy enforcement at the 5G SBA": <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-244335
21	LEN	Conclusion of security evaluation and monitoring: Requirements for security evaluation and monitoring. i.e., The NF collects information about potential abnormal SBI call flows as defined for the communication models in Annex E of TS 23.50, e.g. messages out of sequence.	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	11-15 Nov, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) Updates and Clean-up of KI#1 Conclusion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S3-245182

22	LEN	Requirements for security evaluation and monitoring. PEP and PDP roles in SBA. i.e., For security policy enforcement and improved access control decisions based on security evaluation and monitoring results following aspects are recommended. An NF acting as a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) in SBA performs actions based on security evaluation results/outcome (e.g., in case of NF being identified/suspected to be compromised) during NF service requests (e.g., NF service discovery, access token requests, NF service update) and there may be more than one PEP within the SBA.	3GPP SA3	WP4 WP5	11-15 Nov, 2024	Following contributions were approved for 3GPP SA3 Release 19 for Security Assumptions for TR 33.794 (Study on enablers for Zero Trust Security) - General Recommendations for Conclusion 2 Policy Enforcement: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> S3-245184
23	TID	New work item in ETSI TC-SAI on privacy aspects of AI/ML systems https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=70011	ETSI TC SAI	WP2 WP3 WP5	9 Feb 2024	New work-item approved
24	TID	Post Quantum Cryptography – Guidelines for Telco Use Cases https://www.gsma.com/newsroom/gsma_resources/pq-03-post-quantum-cryptography-guidelines-for-telecom-use-cases/	GSMA	WP2	16b Feb 2024	Approved and published by GSMA TG
25	TID	Third Post Quantum Seminar at MWC. Speaker by invitation of the MWC organizers: https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/agenda/sessions/4509-third-post-quantum-network-seminar	GSMA	WP2	22 Feb 2024	Presented and discussed during MWC 2024
26	TID	Speaker at the GSMA SEC CON 2024 by invitation of the MWC organizers https://www.mwcbarcelona.com/agenda/sessions/4403-gsma-sec-con---securing-the-future-with-artificial-intelligence	GSMA	WP2	29 Feb 2024	Presented and discussed during MWC 2024
27	TID	Proposal to address capability exposure (NaaS) via ZSM integration fabric	ETSI ZSM	WP2, WP4	5 March 2024	Discussed and agreement on building a new work-item on it

		https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2024//ZSM(24)00065_Chairman_Perspective_-_ZSM_26.pptx				
28	TID	Creation of the WIMSE WG, focused on use of identity mechanisms for compute and network workloads: https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/wimse/	IETF Security Area	WP2, WP4	7 March 2024	Working group created
29	TID	Side meeting on terminology (see https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/119/sidemeetings). We progress with the ASSET and ENTITLEMENT concepts proposed by ALMO Side meeting on liaison to other SDOs (see https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/119/sidemeetings) Update on ALMO proposal (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-palmero-ivy-ps-almo/ and https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-palmero-ivy-ps-almo/)	IETF IVY	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Inventory terminology clarified and incorporated in adopted drafts. Progress with the entitlement concept
30	TID	NASR side meeting at IETF 119 Organizer (see https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/119/sidemeetings , https://github.com/liuchunchi/nasr_side_meeting) Charter proposal: https://github.com/liuchunchi/draft-liu-nasr-requirements Architectural proposal: https://github.com/liuchunchi/nasr_side_meeting/blob/main/%5Btelefonica%5D%20Architecture%20Proposal%20--%20NASR-PoT%2BTPR.pdf	IETF Security and Routing Areas	WP2 WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
31	TID	Update on “External Transaction ID for Configuration Tracing” (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-netconf-configuration-tracing/) focused on enhancing telemetry and configuration data	IETF NETCO NF	WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication

32	TID	Update on “Applying COSE Signatures for YANG Data Provenance” (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-lopez-opsawg-yang-provenance/), focused on providing secure monitoring and configuration data	IETF NETMOD	WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication
33	TID	Proposal for the new NMOP WG, Identify existing and anticipated operational issues arising from the near-term deployment of network management technologies, and to consider potential solutions or workarounds for those issues.	IETF Operations Area	WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Group creation (https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/nmop/about/)
34	TID	IBN Side meeting (https://wiki.ietf.org/meeting/119/sidemeetings and https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/119/materials/slides-119-nmrg-chairs-slides) Interconnection intents draft (https://www.ietf.org/archive/id/draft-contreras-nmrg-interconnection-intents-04.txt)	IETF NMARG	WP2 WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Update on NMARG objectives. Internet draft progressing
35	TID	Updates on telemetry documents: “A Data Manifest for Contextualized Telemetry Data” (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest/) “Applying COSE Signatures for YANG Data Provenance” (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-lopez-opsawg-yang-provenance/)	IETF OPSAWG	WP2 WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication
36	TID	Introduction of the NASR concepts (https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/119/materials/slides-119-rats-network-attestation-for-secure-routing-nasr and https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/119/materials/agenda-119-rats-02)	IETF RATS	WP2 WP4 WP5	18 March 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
37	TID	Side meeting on SKEX (Symmetric Key Exchange framework) A proposal for facilitating Symmetric Key Exchange, inspired	IETF Security Area	WP4	18 March 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG

		by the interfaces defined in ETSI QKD004/014 https://www.ietf.org/mailman/listinfo/skex and https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/bofreq-aelmans-symmetric-key-exchange-skex/				
38	TID	SPICE (BoF) https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/119/materials/agenda-119-spice-00 and https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/spice/about/ Application of privacy-aware credential usage. Close to become a WG, once there is convergence on the boundaries wrt W3C	IETF Security Area	WP2 WP4	18 March 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
39	TID	WIMSE: Identity issues for workload in heterogenous environments, as a base for security mechanisms Identification of applicable base technologies and architecture aspects	IETF Security Area	WP2 WP4	18 March 2024	Group creation: https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/wimse/about/
40	TID	Call to action to restructure ZSM work. Either ordered closing or revamp focused on simplifying service interactions https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2024//ZSM(24)00118_Chairman_Perspective_-_ZSM_27.pptx	ETSI ZSM	WP7	15 May 2024	Presented and discussed by the ZSM community at ZSM#27 meeting
41	TID	Discussions and edition of the specification on intent concepts https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/Open/Drafts/016_IntentDrvCL/ZSM-016_IntentDrvCLv010.zip https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM27	ETSI ZSM	WP2, WP4	15 May 2024	ZSM016 advancing to publication
42	TID	Discussions and edition of use cases and procedures for NDT integration ACROSS, EXIGENCE, Hexa-X II, HORSE, iTrust6G, PRIVATEER, ROBUST https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/Open/Drafts/0018_NDT_norm/ZS	ETSI ZSM	WP4 WP6	15 May 2024	ZSM018 advancing to publication

		M-018_NDT_normv001.docx https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM27				
43	TID	New work-item on AI Agent based Next Generation Core Networks https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=72234	ETSI ENI	WP3 WP5	12 Jun 2024	Work-item approved
44	TID	Creation of the SPICE WG, focused on the enhancement of security patterns for credentials https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/spice/	IETF Security Area	WP2 WP4	14 Jun 2024	Working group created
45	TID	Study on AI/ML End-to-end Framework. (AI/ML E2E FW): https://portal.3gpp.org/desktopmodules/WorkItem/WorkItemDetails.aspx?workItemId=1040084	3GPP SA Plenary	WP2 WP3 WP5	24 Jun 2024	Work-item approved
46	TID	A proposal for moving ETI (Encrypted Traffic Integration) work into TC-CYBER and increase impact	ETI TC CYBER	WP7	27 Jun 2024	ETI work integrated in TC CYBER
47	TID	New version of the evolved CLAS architecture: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-contreras-coinrg-clas-evolution-03	IETF COINRG	WP2	23 Jul 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication
48	TID	Draft on knowledge graph application to network OAM: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-marcas-nmop-knowledge-graph-yang-03 Update on the application of knowledge graphs at the NMOP meeting: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/agenda-120-nmop/	IETF NMOP	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication
49	TID	Co-authoring https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-voit-rats-trustworthy-path-routing-10 , on trustworthy path attestation	IETF RATS	WP4 WP6	23 Jul 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication

50	TID	Update on the proposal for describing augmentation and addressing reverse dependencies at the Hackathon: draft-lincla-netconf-yang-library-augmentation (https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/120/hackathon)	IETF Hackathon	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Contribution to the practical approach to telemetry metadata
51	TID	Intro on knowledge graph application at NMRG https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/120/materials/agenda-120-nmrg-03	IETF NMRG	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Presented and discussed at IETF 120
52	TID	New version of the YANG data manifest draft: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest-04 Update on the YANG data manifest: https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/120/materials/agenda-120-opsawg-01	IETF OPSAWG	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication
53	TID	New version of the YANG provenance draft: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-lopez-opsawg-yang-provenance-03 Update on the YANG provenance draft: https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/120/materials/agenda-120-opsawg-01	IETF OPSAWG	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication
54	TID	Organizer and contributor to the AI4NET side meeting on applicability of AI techniques, including data quality and DT considerations, in network management: https://github.com/danielkinguk/ai4network/blob/main/ietf120/agenda.md	IETF Operations Area	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	23 Jul 2024	Progressing towards the creation of new activities in IETF
55	TID	New version of ALMO lifecycle management model drafts: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-palmero-ivy-ps-almo-02	IETF IVY	WP2 WP4 WP5	23 Jul 2024	Internet draft progressing towards publication

		https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-palmero-ivy-dmalmo-02 Update on the ALMO lifecycle management model: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/agenda-120-ivy/				
56	TID	Introduction to confidential workloads for network OAM at the side meeting on “Trusted and Confidential Workloads” https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/120/sidemeetings	IETF OPS and Security Areas	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Presented and discussed to explore new IETF activity
57	TID	New version of NASR requirements draft: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-liu-nasr-requirements-02 New version of NASR architecture draft: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/pdf/draft-liu-nasr-architecture-00 Introduction to path validation scenarios and contribution to the charter discussion at the NASR BoF: https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/nasr/about/	IETF Security and Routing Areas	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
58	TID	Update on use cases and best practices for IBN at the NMRG meeting: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/agenda-120-nmrg/	IETF NMRG	WP2 WP4	23 Jul 2024	Presented and discussed to explore new IETF activity
59	TID	Contributions to the discussion on the NMRG research agenda: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/agenda-120-nmrg/	IETF NMRG	WP2 WP7	23 Jul 2024	Presented and discussed to explore new IETF activity
60	TID	Discussion on the role of standards and the Telco industry in what relates to the European AI Act	CEN/CE NELEC	WP2 WP7	26 Jul 2024	Ongoing discussions regarding the future Standardization Requests from EC
61	TID	New version of Internet-Draft draft-jeong-i2nsf-security-management-automation: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-jeong-i2nsf-security-management-automation/	IETF I2NSF	WP2 WP4	27 Jul 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication

62	TID	Chair reflections on work to support NaaS by the interaction of autonomous multi-domain management, to address anomalies in closed loops, and to consider the migration from automation to autonomy: https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM28 https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2024//ZSM(24)000181_ZSM_28_Meeting_Report.docx	ETSI ZSM	WP7	27 Aug 2024	Presented and discussed by the ZSM community at ZSM#28 meeting
63	TID	Coordination with ITU-T initiative on AI-native networks (LS on references to work on AI enablers and lifecycle management of closed loops) and with IRTF work on NDT (planning for a joint meeting by ZSM#29) https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM28 https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2024//ZSM(24)000181_ZSM_28_Meeting_Report.docx	ETSI ZSM	WP7	27 Aug 2024	Presented and discussed by the ZSM community at ZSM#28 meeting
64	TID	Discussions on the requirements on issues for intent fulfilment, both for intent owners and handlers in ZSM016 (https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM28 https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2024//ZSM(24)000181_ZSM_28_Meeting_Report.docx)	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP4	27 Aug 2024	ZSM016 advancing to publication
65	TID	Joint session between ZSM and F5G on joint activities regarding NaaS and intent-based management of next-generation fixed networks https://portal.etsi.org/Meetings.aspx#/meeting?MtgId=48289 and https://portal.etsi.org/Contribution.aspx?MeetingId=48289	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP4	27 Aug 2024	Presented and discussed by the ZSM community at ZSM#28 meeting. Ongoing collaboration
66	TID	Call to action on the creation of a new Technical Committee on data solutions (TC DATA) in ETSI	ETSI Board	WP2 WP7	24 Sep 2024	Ongoing discussions leading to a formal proposal to be

		https://docbox.etsi.org/Board/2024_Board/BOARD(24)149_050_Call_to_Action_on_Data_Infrastructures.docx https://docbox.etsi.org/Board/2024_Board/BOARD(24)149_070_TC_Data_Overview_Presentation.pptx				discussed in January 2025
67	TID	3GPP Rel-19 WID proposal on Management aspect of Network Digital Twin	3GPP SA5	WP2 WP4 WP6	16 Oct 2024	Proposed new work item
68	TID	New version of the I-D on configuration tracing: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-netconf-configuration-tracing/	IETF OPSAWG	WP4 WP5	21 Oct 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication
69	TID	New version of draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest/), on telemetry metadata	IETF OPSAWG	WP4 WP5	7 Nov 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication
70	TID	An entitlement model for the management of network inventories, submitted and presented at the IVY WG meeting: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-mcd-ivy-entitlements-inventory/	IETF IVY	WP2 WP4 WP5	7 Nov 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication
71	TID	Side meeting on the NASR proposal: https://wiki.ietf.org/meeting/121/sidemeetings . Discussions on trust domains, attestation and service models	IETF Security and Routing Areas	WP2, WP4	7 Nov 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
72	TID	Introduction to the trusted confidential computing mesh approach at the RATS meeting: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/agenda-121-rats/	IETF RATS	WP2, WP4, WP6	7 Nov 2024	Considering a new internet draft
73	TID	New version and presentation at NMOP WG meeting of the draft on network incident modelling: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-nmop-network-incident-modelling/	IETF NMOP	WP2 WP3	7 Nov 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication

		raft-ietf-nmop-network-incident-yang/		WP4 WP5		
74	TID	Introduction to knowledge graphs at the side meeting on AI4NET: https://wiki.ietf.org/meeting/121/sidemeetings and https://github.com/danielkinguk/ai4network/blob/main/ietf121/agenda-121.md	IETF Security and Routing Areas	WP2 WP4 WP6	7 Nov 2024	Considering a new internet draft
75	TID	Update on the CLAS SDN-enabled architecture and presentation at the NMRG meeting: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-contreras-nmrg-clas-evolution/	IETF NMRG and COINRG	WP2	7 Nov 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication
76	TID	Update on the AINEMA approach for AI-enabled network management and presentation at the NMRG meeting: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-pedro-nmrg-ai-framework/	IETF NMRG	WP2 WP3 WP5	7 Nov 2024	Internet drafts progressing towards publication
77	TID	The NeoTec side meeting discussing a potential new WG on network-hosted datacentres suitable to new agent-based and data intensive applications (federated ML, distributed AI...): https://wiki.ietf.org/meeting/121/sidemeetings	IETF Security and Routing Areas	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5	7 Nov 2024	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
78	TID	Joint NMRG/ZSM meeting on intent and NDT technologies: https://github.com/danielkinguk/nmrg-zsm-session/blob/main/agenda.md	IETF NMRG and ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP4	7 Nov 2024	Identifying new work-items and documents in both groups
79	TID	Chair perspectives, analysing recent meetings with IRTF and exposing the future options for the ISG continuation, with a special focus on demonstrative deliverables via PoC activity: http://portal.etsi.org/ngppapp/ContributionCreation.aspx?primarykeys=302042	ETSI ZSM	WP7	12 Nov 2024	Continue ZSM leadership
80	TID	New work item on a ZSM Framework for NaaS (Network as a Service) – ZSM019:	ETSI ZSM	WP4 WP6	12 Nov 2024	Work-item approved

		https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.aspx?WKI_ID=73742				
81	TID	New work item on the applicability of distributed agents in zero-touch management, and in alignment with the ZSM architecture – ZSM020: https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.aspx?WKI_ID=73740	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP4 WP6	12 Nov 2024	Work-item approved
82	TID	Last call for draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest, on telemetry metadata: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest/	IETF OPSAWG	WP4 WP6		Close to RFC publication
83	TID	Invitation to the IAB workshop on the Next Era of Network Management Operations (NEMOPS): https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/nemopsws/about/	IETF IAB	WP2 WP7	27 Nov 2024	Participation by invitation
84	TID	New version of the telemery provenance I-D proposal: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-lopez-opsawg-yang-provenance/	IETF OPSAWG	WP2 WP4 WP6	5 Jan 2025	Internet draft progressing towards publication
85	TID	IETF BoF request on secure exchange of symmetric keys: https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/bofreq-aelmans-skex-symmetric-key-establishment-and-exchange/	IETF Security Area	WP2 WP4 WP6	5 Jan 2025	Progressing towards the creation of an IETF WG
86	TID	GSMA Document on NTN and PQC Use Case: https://membergateway.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/wg-TG-PQTN/ChangeRequests/NTN%20and%20PQC%20Use%20Case/NTN%20Use%20Case.docx	GSMA PQTN-TF	WP2 WP6	21 Jan 2025	Sent to the Technology Group for publication
87	TID	GSMA Document on PQC in the Internet of Things (IoT) Context: https://membergateway.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/wg-TG-	GSMA PQTN-TF	WP2 WP6	27 Jan 2025	Sent to Technology Group for publication

		PQTN/ChangeRequests/IoT%20and%20PQC%20document%20(PQTN%20Approval)/PQ.04%20Post%20Quantum%20Cryptography%20in%20IoT%20context%20v1.0.docx				
88	TID	Establishment of a new Technical Committee on Data Solutions (TC DATA) https://docbox.etsi.org/C_Letter/CL2025/CL(25)_4173_TC_DATA_Establishment.pdf	ETSI	WP2 WP4 WP7	12 Feb 2025	Approved by ETSI Board
89	TID	3GPP 6G Workshop. Specific mentions in the chair's summary to: * Increased security, integrity, and privacy are required from day one, incorporating zero trust principles and post-quantum security measures. * An upper layer on top of SBA: AI INTENT MANAGEMENT LAYER https://www.3gpp.org/ftp/workshop/2025-03-10_3GPP_6G_WS/Docs/6GWS-250038.zip	3GPP SA	WP2 WP7	14 Mar 2025	Recommendations published by SA chair. To be considered in the corresponding 3GPP releases
90	TID	HACKATHON – Project on demonstrating the microservice implementation of YANG data provenance https://wiki.ietf.org/en/meeting/122/hackathon https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-hackathon-sessd-on-the-use-of-yang-provenance-signatures-01	IETF Hackathon	WP2 WP4	15 Mar 2025	Demonstration run and presented. Discussions with several interested parties. Progressing with draft publication as RFC
91	TID	Update and presentation on YANG data provenance, that will go for the adoption call by the WG https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-lopez-opsawg-yang-	IETF OPSA WG	WP2 WP4	17 Mar 2025	Progressing towards WG adoption and RFC publication

		<p>provenance/ https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-opsawg-applying-cose-signatures-for-yang-data-provenance-00)</p>				
92	TID	<p>Update and presentation on telemetry data manifest</p> <p>https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-opsawg-a-data-manifest-for-contextualized-telemetry-data-00 https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-opsawg-collected-data-manifest/</p>	IETF OPSA WG	WP2 WP4	17 Mar 2025	Progressing towards RFC publication
93	TID	<p>Discussion on data residency</p> <p>https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/agenda-122-wimse-04 https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-wimse-wimse-impact-on-data-residency-requirements-for-handling-sensitive-data-01</p>	IETF WIMSE WG	WP2 WP4	17 Mar 2025	Considering an appropriate WG to progress with this work
94	TID	<p>NASR – BoF, as convenor and presenter of the problem statement</p> <p>https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/agenda-122-nasr-01 https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-nasr-nasr-use-cases-00</p>	IETF Security Area	WP4 WP7	18 Mar 2025	Discussions ongoing within Security Area, either towards a new WG or as activities within the RATS WG
95	TID	<p>SKEX – BoF, as convenor and presenter of the relevant use cases</p> <p>https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/agenda-122-skex-02 https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-skex-02</p>	IETF Security Area	WP4 WP7	19 Mar 2025	Discussions ongoing within the Security Area, towards a focused scope definition

		122-skex-presentation-slides-v03-00				
96	TID	Brief introduction to TC DATA and the application of semantic models for network OAM https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/agenda-122-nmop-04 https://datatracker.ietf.org/meeting/122/materials/slides-122-nmop-1-chairs-slides-01	IETF NMOP	WP2 WP4 WP7	19 Mar 2025	Update shared with the WG most focused on operational goals in the IETF
97	TID	Side meeting on Data Secure Processing for AI, introducing questions on data governance https://trello.com/c/JwtMkJzN/56-1315-1445-enabling-data-security-trust-and-privacy-for-ai-in-future-network	IETF / IRTF	WP2 WP7	20 Mar 2025	Ongoing discussion, trying to define a clear scope for the work
98	TID	New work-item in ETSI TC CYBER: Universal Cybersecurity Information Exchange Framework - Repository (UCYBEX) https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74827	ETSI TC CYBER	WP2 WP3 WP4 WP7	21 Mar 2025	Work item approved by TC CYBER
99	TID	Appointment as TC DATA chair https://docbox.etsi.org/DATA/DATA/05-Contributions/2025/DATA(25)000004_DATA_01_-_Draft_Meeting_Report.docx	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Only candidate, ratified at the opening of the first TC DATA meeting
100	TID	Reflections on TC DATA initial steps https://docbox.etsi.org/DATA/DATA/05-Contributions/2025/DATA(25)000051_Chair_Perspectives_for_DATA_01.pptx	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Shared after appointment as chair
101	TID	Position statement on data activities related to next-generation networks	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Presented and discussed at TC DATA#01

		https://docbox.etsi.org/DATA/DATA/05-Contributions/2025/DATA(25)000018_Discussion_paper_on_Sensing_AI_and_Trustworthy_data_in_mobi.docx				
102	TID	Position statement and presentation on data governance and semantic interoperability (https://docbox.etsi.org/DATA/DATA/05-Contributions/2025/DATA(25)000042r1_Position_Paper_on_Data_Governance_and_Semantic_Interoperabil.docx) https://docbox.etsi.org/DATA/DATA/05-Contributions/2025/DATA(25)000046_A_Position_Statement_on_Data_Governance_and_Semantic_Intero.pptx	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Presented and discussed at TC DATA#01
103	TID	New work-item on Smart contracts https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74839	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Approved by TC DATA
104	TID	New work-item on Oracles for Smart Contracts executed in Electronic Ledgers https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74879	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Approved by TC DATA
105	TID	New work-item on data quality metrics https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74875	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Approved by TC DATA
106	TID	New work-item on Landscape of Relevant Standards and Technologies for Data https://portal.etsi.org/webapp	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Approved by TC DATA

		/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74880				
107	TID	Four new work-items on NGSI-LD evolution https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74870 https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74871 https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74872 https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=74873	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Approved by TC DATA
108	TID	TC DATA introduction at the 6GFORGE event https://telcoforge.com/agenda-6g-forge-2025/ https://telcoforge.com/speakers-6g-forge-2025/	ETSI TC DATA	WP2 WP4	16 Apr 2025	Presented and discussed
109	TID	Chair reflections on the next term for ZSM, considering alternatives and future structure: https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM30 https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2025/ZSM(25)000082_ZSM_30_Meeting_Report.docx https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2025/ZSM(25)000080r2_Chairman_Perspective_-_ZSM_30.pptx	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP7	23 Apr 2025	Presented at ISG ZSM#30 in Beijing
110	TID	Discussions on the trust concept, and the use of existing mechanisms, such as LoA (NFV-SEC007) and Trust Management Service (ZSM014) in ZSM017	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP7	24 Apr 2025	Contributions made and incorporated in the current version of ZSM017

		https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM30				
111	TID	Discussions on multi-domain scenarios, agent supervision, identity management, and supervision mechanisms in ZSM020 https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM30	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP7	24 Apr 2025	Contributions made and incorporated in the current version of ZSM020
112	TID	Discussion on the applicability of smart contracts (as described in ZSM016) in NaaS scenarios, as defined in ZSM019 https://pad-public.etsi.org/p/ZSM30	ETSI ZSM	WP2 WP7	24 Apr 2025	Contributions made and incorporated in the current version of ZSM019
113	TID	Joint session with CCSA TC17, exploring collaboration on aspects related to Autonomous Networks, NDTs, agents and LLMs https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2025/ZSM(25)000029_ETSI_ZSM30_CCSA_TC7_workshop_planning.docx https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/ZSM/05-CONTRIBUTIONS/2025/ZSM(25)000082_ZSM_30_Meeting_Report.docx	ETSI ZSM	WP7	25 Apr 2025	Presentation of ongoing ZSM activities and chairing on the concluding open discussion

7 Exploitation of the Project Results

7.1 Overview

The exploitation strategy of the iTrust6G project follows a structured approach aimed at maximizing the impact of its outcomes across a wide range of stakeholders. The strategy is designed to evolve throughout the project lifecycle, adapting to emerging insights and opportunities. It encompasses both individual and joint exploitation plans, integrating communication, dissemination, and engagement activities.

7.2 Strategy

The high-level strategy for the exploitation can be summed up as:

- **Identification of innovative assets:** The project will identify technological components and add-value to services to be delivered to target users, emphasizing trust as a governing principle. Identify and characterize Key Exploitable Results (KERs), analyse the market and competitors, and define the value proposition.
- **Market analysis:** A thorough market analysis will be conducted to identify target markets, segmentation, competitor positioning, and emerging trends. This analysis will encompass sectors such as telecommunications, network infrastructure, IoT, and beyond. It will assess market positioning, competitor landscape, and emerging trends to inform strategic decision-making. This market analysis will inform the definition of exploitation models and the target groups that we should aim to connect with.
- **Intellectual Property Right (IPR) management strategy:** An analytical IPR management strategy will be documented based on project Consortium Agreement (CA), guiding joint and individual exploitation efforts. This strategy will delineate how intellectual property generated by the project will be managed, ensuring effective collaboration among partners while safeguarding individual and joint exploitation capabilities.
- **Definition of exploitation models:** Various commercial and non-commercial exploitation models will be defined and evaluated, considering sustainability and viability. These models will encompass avenues such as licensing schemes, partnerships, and direct commercialization. The aim is to identify the most viable and sustainable approaches for maximizing the project's impact.
- **Business model evaluation:** The sustainability and viability of business models will be assessed, including licensing schemes, pricing, and alternative solutions. Alternative solutions for delivering project solutions and services to stakeholders will also be explored, ensuring alignment with long-term objectives.
- **Validation through demonstrators:** The efficacy of the exploitation activities will be validated through iTrust6G's demonstrator projects. These real-world implementations will provide valuable insights into market acceptance, user feedback, and scalability, validating the viability of the chosen exploitation strategies.

7.3 Identification of innovative assets

The main goal is to identify and describe innovative assets, focusing on technology and value-added services for specific user groups. Below in Table 7-1 are the Key Exploitable Results for iTrust6G.

Table 7-1 Key Exploitable Results

No	Partners	Key Exploitable Result	Open Contributions	Type	Exploitation Potential	TRL (Initial / Target)
1	UC3M	Intent Processor	Yes	Product	Educational, Research, Support for commercial service management	2/6
2	UC3M / TID	Explainability	Yes	Product	Educational, Research, Support for commercial service management	2/5
3	NTUA	Collaborative Threat Intelligence	No	Product	Educational, Research	1/4
4	POLITO	Remediation Manager	Yes	Product	Educational, Research	1/4
5	POLITO	Remediation Playbook Repo	Yes	Repository	Educational, Research	1/4
6	I2CAT / ADR / POLITO	Static Trust Assessment	Yes	Product	I2CAT - ADR - Commercial - POLITO -	I2CAT - ADR - 1/4 - POLITO -
7	PDM / POLITO	AI Trust Evaluator	Yes	Product	Research, Societal	1/3
8	POLITO	Remote Attestation Engine	Yes	Product	Educational, Research	1/4
9	NTUA	Forensic Analyzer	Yes	Product	Educational, Research	1/4
10	LEN	Service Orchestrator	Yes	Product	Research	1/4
11	TID	Identity Provider	Maybe Yes	Product	Research, support for commercial service provisioning	3/7

12	TID / UC3M	Policy Decision Point	Yes	Product	Educational, Research, Support for commercial service management	3/7
13	POLITO	Risk Assessor	Yes	Product	Educational, Research	1/4
14	PDM	SIEM	Yes	Product	Commercial	5/7
15	ADR	Threat detection & classification	No	Product	Commercial	3/5
16	NTUA	Federated Learning Models	Yes	Knowledge / IP	Educational, Research	2/5
17	PDM	Trust Inference	Yes	Product	Commercial, Research	1/4
18	POLITO	Remediator	Yes	Product	Educational, Research	1/4
19	TID	Evidence Repository	Yes	Product	Research, Support for commercial service management	3/7
20	I2CAT	Counter Measure Recommender	Yes	Product	Research, Commercial	5/6
21	POLITO	Attester	No	Product	Educational, Research	1/4

7.4 Market analysis

The European 6G market is on the cusp of a significant transformation, with projections indicating a growth from \$0.32 billion in 2028 to \$240.02 billion by 2035, representing a CAGR of 100.72%.

This exponential growth is attributed to the increasing demand for low-latency networks and the expanding use of edge computing devices and internet services. Europe's proactive stance in 6G research and development, coupled with substantial investments from both nations and businesses, positions it as a leader in the next-generation wireless communication technology [2].

7.4.1 Impact on European industries

6G technology promises to revolutionise various sectors across the European Union by enabling ultra-high data rates, low-latency communication, massive number of connectivity, and the integration of artificial intelligence. Industries such as automotive, construction, energy, healthcare, agriculture, entertainment, and manufacturing are poised to benefit significantly from the advancements in 6G technology. iTrust6G supports the development of new technologies and applications, fostering a Europe-wide network of small

and medium-sized enterprises, startups, and Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) partners. This collaborative effort is expected to set new standards and create advanced developments in real-time capable sensor and control technology, edge cloud technologies, and digital twins for robotics and machine tools [3].

Several sectors can benefit from 6G, to name a few:

- Healthcare: Where telesurgery can allow surgeons to perform remote surgeries with real-time, high-definition video and haptic feedback [4].
- Automotive: Can support autonomous driving with real-time communication between vehicles and infrastructure, precise positioning, and 360° environment sensing. Leading to safer robot-taxis and autonomous vehicles [5].
- Manufacturing: Improving ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) for industrial automation and real-time control [6].
- Entertainment: 6G can enable real-time 8k video streaming or cloud gaming, providing low-latency and high-fidelity [7].

7.4.2 Geographical deployment

The European Union's commitment to high-performing digital connectivity infrastructure is evident in its digital decade targets, which aim to provide all EU households with access to a fixed gigabit network and all populated areas with 5G coverage by 2030. As the groundwork for 6G is laid, the EU is strengthening partnerships with other countries, such as the US and Japan, to accelerate cooperation and develop a common vision and industry roadmap for 6G wireless communication systems. These collaborations are crucial for addressing the challenges of privacy, cybersecurity, and environmental impact associated with the deployment of 6G networks [8]. Outside of EU, the old 5G front runners are key markets to engage with, i.e., South Korea, China, Japan, and India from Asia, and Brazil in Latin America, and from North America, both USA and Canada as future key players.

7.5 Exploitation target groups

Effective exploitation of **iTrust6G**, should include a targeted strategy to engage key stakeholders, including 6G network operators, academic institutions, and standardization bodies, ensuring the product's successful deployment, widespread adoption, and alignment with emerging industry standards.

7.5.1 Operators of 6G Networks

As a key target group for the commercial exploitation of the **iTrust6G** project, 6G network operators Table 7-2 will play a crucial role in the deployment and widespread adoption of the project's innovative solutions.

Table 7-2 Exploitation Target Group: Operators

Operator	Target Services	Partners
Telefonica	<p>As one of the main global network operators, with operations in the EU (Germany and Spain), the UK, and most of Latin America (with special relevance of Brazil), Telefonica would be highly interesting in enhancing the trustworthiness of 5G-Advanced and 6G services in all its operations.</p> <p>Zero-trust, intent-based service management and consumption, and the availability of transparent evidence and explainability mechanisms constitute essential elements to improve trustworthiness, especially in the approach of network-of-networks contemplated as essential paradigm for 6G.</p>	TID, UC3M

	The 5TONIC testbed will constitute an excellent scenario to demonstrate and evaluate iTrust6G for Telefonica’s Business Units	
Vodafone Portugal	<p>One of the 3 big telecom operator providing 5G coverage in Portugal, and on the pole-position for adopting 6G as a differentiator factor.</p> <p>Security features: By integrating iTrust6G's advanced security solutions, Vodafone Portugal could offer superior protection against cyber threats, which is increasingly important for both individual and business customers. This would be a strong selling point against competitors who may not have the same level of security infrastructure.</p> <p>Innovative services: The iTrust6G project's focus on intelligent security and trust orchestration could enable Vodafone Portugal to develop new, innovative services that leverage the enhanced capabilities of 6G networks, such as ultra-reliable low-latency communications and massive machine-type communications.</p> <p>Improved network performance: The adoption of iTrust6G's software-defined networking and Zero-trust security principles could lead to more efficient network management and better performance, which Vodafone Portugal could market as a competitive advantage.</p> <p>Customer Trust: By being at the forefront of adopting cutting-edge security technologies from iTrust6G, Vodafone Portugal could position itself as a trusted leader in the market, attracting customers who prioritize the security and reliability of their telecommunications provider.</p> <p>Market differentiation: Vodafone Portugal could use the iTrust6G project's outcomes to differentiate itself by emphasizing its commitment to sustainability and future technologies, as seen in their collaboration with Ericsson for energy-saving radio upgrades [9].</p>	PDM
Orange Polska (Poland)	<p>Orange Polska is a market leader operator in Poland. Improved network performance is in the pool position to adopt AI Driven Network optimization tools.</p> <p>Security features and Innovative services by integrating iTrust6G AI Trust Evaluation and adopting the zero trust principles, can provide B2B customers with top-of-the-line security services.</p> <p>Market Differentiation and Customer Trust having the latest technological bells and whistles gives them an extra argument to fend off market share attacks from priced based operators.</p>	PDM

7.5.2 Scientists and academia

Target academic and scientific organisations can be categorised as:

- Collaborative research and development
 - *Engage in Joint Projects:* Establish partnerships with academic institutions to work on joint research projects that leverage iTrust6G results.
 - *Funding and Grants:* Seek funding opportunities and grants that support collaborative research between industry and academia, focusing on the development and application of iTrust6G.
- Knowledge transfer and education

- *Workshops and Seminars:* Organize workshops, seminars, and webinars to disseminate knowledge about iTrust6G technologies and their potential applications to the academic community. As presented in Section 4.3.
- Academic publications and standards
 - *Research Publications:* Encourage joint publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences to showcase the advancements and findings from iTrust6G research. As presented in Section 4.1.
 - *Contribution to Standards:* Involve academic partners in the process of contributing to and shaping the standards for 6G technologies, as presented in Section 6.

7.5.3 Policy Makers

Policy makers could be target of the project results exploitations in the following ways:

- Showcase technological innovations and benefits
 - *Demonstrate advanced security features:* Highlight the project's advancements in security, such as the zero-trust architecture and intelligent security orchestration, to address policymakers' concerns about national security and cyber threats. Demonstration scheduled for the 26th of April in Belmonte, Portugal to showcase to a group of local policy makers the benefits of the technological innovations of iTrust6G.
- Engage in policy dialogue and advocacy
 - *Policy workshops and seminars:* Organize workshops and seminars with key stakeholders, including policymakers, to discuss the implications of 6G technologies and the need for supportive policy frameworks. Presented in Section 4.3.

7.5.4 Wider public

iTrust6G is committed to fostering an environment of openness and collaborative engagement across various sectors, including academia, industry, and governmental bodies. The project's focus on standardization and open-source activities is designed to achieve several key objectives:

- **Advocating for open standards:** iTrust6G aims to champion the creation and widespread adoption of open standards. These standards are crucial for ensuring interoperability and the ability to work across different platforms and technologies. A significant part of this effort involves working closely with open-source initiatives like CAMARA (<https://camaraproject.org/>) which supports the implementation of the GSMA's Open Gateway APIs, thereby facilitating seamless integration and communication across diverse systems. Presented in section 6.
- **Engaging with industry initiatives:** The project seeks to forge strong partnerships with industry-led groups and consortia, such as the 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) and the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA). These collaborations are essential for aligning iTrust6G's standardization efforts with the practical needs and requirements of the industry, ensuring that the project's outcomes are both relevant and beneficial to the broader telecommunications ecosystem. Presented in section 6.
- **Promoting knowledge exchange:** iTrust6G is dedicated to enhancing knowledge sharing and fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration. By organizing and participating in workshops, conferences, and other events, the project aims to create opportunities for interaction and exchange among experts from various standardization bodies. Additionally, these gatherings serve as platforms for researchers and developers to discuss advancements, challenges, and opportunities in the realm of 6G technologies, furthering the collective understanding and progress in this field.

7.5.5 Open-Source

iTrust6G targets Open-Source communities for contributing developed codes, the following strategy will be pursued:

- **Stakeholder identification:** Begin by pinpointing the essential stakeholders and partners who will participate in the standardization process. During the project, TID and LENOVO are the main partners that contribute to the standardization process and their contributions can be seen in Chapter 6.
- **Scope definition:** Clearly outline the extent of the standardization and open-source efforts. This involves identifying the critical technologies to be developed and pinpointing the necessary standards to be established or revised to support these technologies. A preliminary list of relevant standardization bodies and working groups should be included. As we are a few steps ahead we present in this report the current relevant bodies and the contributions already performed by the consortium partners in Chapter 6.
- **Standards body engagement:** Actively collaborate with pertinent standards organizations, such as the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP). The aim is to align the project's standardization efforts with current standards and contribute to the creation of new standards as required.

Trials and testing: Implement trials and testing throughout the project to verify that the developed technologies adhere to the necessary standards and can be implemented reliably and securely. Work has started on iTrust6G 6.1 [10] that aims to present the plans for trials and testing based on the requirements iTrust6G 2.1 [11] and the architecture iTrust6G 2.2 [12].

7.5.6 Relation to SNS projects

iTrust6G places a strong emphasis on networking activities with national and EU bodies, aiming to facilitate the exchange of experiences, gather feedback, foster collaboration, and ultimately support coordinated responses to cyber incidents. Examples of relevant bodies and projects in the cybersecurity domain include ENISA, CERT-EU, ECSO, CyberSec4Europe, SPARTA, Cybersecurity Atlas, CONCORDIA, ECHO, the NIS Cooperation Group, the CSIRTs Network, and the Horizontal Working Party on Cyber Issues (HWP).

iTrust6G is committed to engaging with industrial stakeholders on a global scale, leveraging established contacts within the consortium, particularly through industrial partners and technology providers. Key dissemination and communication efforts include participating in major industrial and trade events to present the project, distribute informational materials, and explore potential partnerships with other exhibitors. A special event will be organized at the project's conclusion to showcase results, demonstrations, business models, and recommendations to policymakers, industry representatives, and the public, aiming to attract around 100 attendees. This conference will be prefaced by a white paper detailing the project's concept, objectives, and outcomes.

iTrust6G acknowledges its obligations under the SNS JU program, including adherence to the organizational structure outlined in its contract and technical annex. The consortium supports the evolution of 6G networks through participation in other SNS projects such as:

- **BeGREEN** focuses on developing radio networks that manage increasing traffic, and service demands while minimizing power consumption.
- **6Green** aims to create a service-based ecosystem that extends communication infrastructure into a sustainable, interconnected, and energy-efficient system across the 5G/6G value chain.
- **NANCY** seeks to introduce a secure and intelligent architecture for B5G wireless networks.

- **RDUST** strives to deliver an integrated 5G-NTN autonomous system with a novel connectivity model for ubiquitous access.

Additionally, several projects are exploring innovative technologies for future commercial network adoption:

- **DETERMINISTIC6G** proposes a new architecture to enhance network performance awareness with time synchronization across domains.
- **ADROIT6G** focuses on AI/ML-powered optimizations across 6G mobile networks for improved design, implementation, operation, and maintenance.
- **PREDICT-6G** aims to develop a Multi-technology Multi-domain Data-Plane (MDP) to improve the reliability and timing of current wired and wireless standards, with a vision for inherently deterministic network design.

7.6 IPR management

At its core, the **iTrust6G** project's overarching aim is to bolster the capacity to tackle and mitigate challenges on cybersecurity, privacy, and data protection. This involves a multifaceted approach that encompasses the creation of innovative software solutions characterized by their creativity, user-friendliness, and affordability. Additionally, the project recognizes the importance of supplementary advisory and training services to empower stakeholders with the knowledge and tools needed to navigate complex digital landscapes safely and securely. Within the **iTrust6G** consortium, there is a dedicated focus on addressing these concerns comprehensively. Through collaborative efforts, the consortium endeavours to develop solutions that not only meet regulatory requirements but also exceed industry standards in terms of effectiveness and accessibility.

The formulation of an IPR strategy within the CA underscores the project's commitment to ensuring that the fruits of its labour are appropriately protected and leveraged for maximum impact. This strategic approach to IPR management is integral to the project's overall exploitation plan, safeguarding its innovations while also facilitating their seamless integration into broader standardization and commercialization processes.

Throughout the project lifecycle, plenary meetings serve as forums for the review and evaluation of internal outcomes. Once per year, an IPR form will be reviewed by each partner and stored on the project repository, coordination lead by PDM with GIGASYST support. This iterative process enables the identification of key ideas and concepts that hold significant potential for advancement and commercialization. By actively engaging in this ongoing dialogue, stakeholders can collaboratively refine their strategies for positioning these ideas within relevant frameworks, thereby maximizing their reach and impact in the broader digital ecosystem.

To uphold the devised strategy for managing the knowledge introduced to **iTrust6G** or generated throughout its development, a meticulous plan has been devised to safeguard IPR, ensuring its protection remains a focal point in all administrative deliberations. It is imperative that prior to the project's commencement, all partners come to a mutual agreement regarding explicit rules governing IP ownership, rights to Background and foreground IP, as well as the handling of confidential information pertaining to IPR. This pivotal decision will be formalised and documented within the CA, a binding contract signed by all partners to establish the legal framework governing their collaboration and mitigate potential issues that may arise over the project's lifespan. Moreover, in alignment with the guidelines outlined in the Guide to Intellectual Property Rules for European projects [13], consortium members will adhere to the CA, ensuring compliance with contractual obligations, including agreements with employees and other personnel who may have entitlements to intellectual property rights.

To ensure the effective management of background and foreground IPs, a clear demarcation will be made between the assets each partner brings to the project (background) and those developed within the project

(foreground). Each partner will meticulously specify their contributions before the project's commencement, with these details documented within the CA. The ownership of foreground knowledge generated within the project will reside with the partner responsible for its creation. In instances where multiple partners contribute to the development of specific knowledge, and it is impossible to discern individual contributions, all involved parties will share equal rights over the resultant knowledge.

7.6.1 Exploitation models

Focusing on the commercialization pathways for iTrust6G technologies, it's essential to identify and select the most appropriate routes to market. These pathways include licensing agreements, technology transfer, joint ventures, or the creation of spin-offs and startups. Each of these routes offers unique advantages and challenges, and the choice among them should be informed by the specific characteristics of the iTrust6G technologies, market demands, and the strategic goals of the project. Here, a set of possible business models tailored to these commercialization pathways are proposed:

- **Licensing agreements:** Licensing agreements allow iTrust6G to grant rights to use its technologies to other companies in exchange for royalties or fees. This model is particularly suitable for technologies that can be integrated into existing products or services, enhancing their value.
 - *Royalty-based licensing:* iTrust6G could offer its technologies to established telecommunications companies under a royalty agreement, where payments are made based on the sales of products incorporating the iTrust6G technologies.
 - *Flat-fee licensing:* For smaller companies or startups, a flat-fee licensing model could be more attractive, providing access to iTrust6G technologies for a fixed fee, making financial planning easier for the licensee.
- **Technology transfer:** Technology transfer involves the formal transfer of iTrust6G technologies to another entity for further development and commercialization. This pathway is ideal for technologies that require significant development before reaching the market.
 - *University partnerships:* Collaborating with universities to further develop and commercialize iTrust6G technologies, leveraging academic expertise and resources.
 - *Public-private partnerships (PPPs):* Engaging in PPPs to support the development and deployment of iTrust6G technologies in public infrastructure projects, benefiting from public funding and support.
- **Joint Ventures:** Joint ventures involve creating a new entity with one or more partners to develop and commercialize iTrust6G technologies. This model is suitable for projects that require substantial investment and expertise from multiple stakeholders.
 - *Co-development model:* Establishing joint ventures with industry leaders to co-develop products or services based on iTrust6G technologies, sharing risks and rewards.
 - *Market expansion ventures:* Forming joint ventures with local companies in target markets to facilitate market entry and adaptation of iTrust6G technologies to local needs.
- **Creation of spin-offs and startups:** Creating spin-offs or startups to commercialize iTrust6G technologies offers the flexibility to focus exclusively on bringing these innovations to market.
 - *technology-specific spin-offs:* Establishing spin-offs focused on specific iTrust6G technologies, attracting investment and talent dedicated to developing and commercializing these innovations.
 - *Incubator/accelerator model:* Launching an incubator or accelerator program to support startups developing applications or services based on iTrust6G technologies, providing mentorship, funding, and resources.

7.7 Joint exploitation plan and activities

Joint exploitation opportunities were compiled in an initial list of KERs. Throughout the projects lifecycle this list will be reviewed and updated according to the needs of pilot's partners and the research results produced. Specifically, during T7.4, which involves regular WP7 meetings, there should be a focus on monitoring and discussing these joint exploitation opportunities.

Table 7-3 iTrust6G Primary Joint Exploitation Plans

KER	Description	Result Type	Owner(s)	Commercial Exploitation Strategy
iTrust6G platform	The iTrust6G platform itself containing all the modules and functionalities.	Product	ALL partners	The partners will jointly evaluate during the project the possibility to create two versions of the platform, one community edition (with only open-source components) and another with commercial products and support.
Security Orchestrator Module	SIEM, AI-Driven Security Orchestration module	Product & Service	NTUA, POLITO, LEN, PDM, i2CAT	<p>As a national academic institute NTUA is not allowed to sell any of the developed modules of iTrust6G in any market. Instead, it will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspire academic research including publications, undergraduate theses, and PhD programs. • Consulting services one similar aspects for other European projects and submitting new proposals. <p>Lenovo, as a leading technology company with a broad portfolio of products and services, could integrate the Security Orchestrator Module into its current offerings, such as edge computing solutions, data centre products, and cloud services.</p> <p>This integration would enhance the security capabilities of these products and services, providing added value to customers and differentiating Lenovo's solutions from competitors.</p> <p>i2CAT will enrich its portfolio relating to security orchestration with the generator of programmable security resources. The commercial exploitation of this technological asset will be evaluated and may conduct to open-source dissemination.</p> <p>Moreover, the new methods will frame further research activities including the preparation of academic publications, undergraduate thesis and PhD programs.</p> <p>PDM will join forces with other industry partners (TID and Lenovo) and demonstrate the extended tools in the SOM, first in the Pilots within the project, and jointly participate in industry wide events (for instance Mobile World Congress) that can showcase the advantages of SOM in an operator's infrastructure.</p> <p>The joint exploitation with the Academic partners will be based on the IP rights agreement to be discussed during the project, leading to licensing of several of the components to be developed by those partners.</p> <p>Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications.</p>

KER	Description	Result Type	Owner(s)	Commercial Exploitation Strategy
Security Service Orchestrator	Tasks: 5.1, 5.2, 5.5 Tools: Service monitoring and detection module	Product & Service	I2CAT, ADR, PDM	Adrestia is focusing in updating the Automation portfolio by introducing a network security service orchestration that will be able to support the vulnerability assessment product and the Robotic Process Automation. The main License scheme foreseen is: Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications. The Joint exploitation strategy will be rooted in the participation of events as a group as well as the approach to the market players (mobile operators, network equipment providers, etc.) offering a unified solution that includes individual licensing of the tools to be developed.
Trust Information Module	Tasks: 3.4, 4.1 Tools: Continuous Diagnostics and Mitigation System, AI-Enabled Threat Intelligence, Vulnerability Detection Module	Product & Service	PDM	Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications
Trust Evaluation Module	Tasks: 4.2 Tools: AI-Driven Trust & Trust algorithm module	Product & Service	PDM, ADR, POLITO	Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications. The Joint Exploitation strategy in this case will start by identifying within the respective organizations, any cybersecurity offerings that can be improved by incorporating the TEM. This analysis will start at the beginning of the project and will run continuously until the end of the project, since market conditions might lead to unforeseeable opportunities
Control Module	Tasks: 4.3 Tools: Authentication module, Access control module, ID Management module, Intent-based security policy module	Product & Service	TID, PDM	Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications
Network slicing and segmentation module	Tasks: 5.5 Tools: Segmentation, Software Defined Parameter Module, Pervasive security programmability	Product & Service	LEN	Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications
Third party application management module	Tasks: 4.1 Tools: Third party application trust management,	Product & Service	ADR	Adrestia is already building an RPA tool that provides third party integration for utilising Adrestia product portfolio. In the specific module we foresee an update specific to 6G Networks. The main License scheme foreseen is: Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications
AI/ML for security automation	Tasks: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 Tools: AI-Enabled Threat Intelligence, Risk Mitigation,	Product & Service	NTUA, ADR, POLITO, PDM	As a national academic institute NTUA is not allowed to sell any of the developed modules of iTrust6G in any market. Instead, it will:

KER	Description	Result Type	Owner(s)	Commercial Exploitation Strategy
	Vulnerability Assessment.			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inspire academic research including publications, undergraduate theses, and PhD programs. Consulting services on similar aspects for other European projects and submitting new proposals. Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications Most of the tools developed in this module will be able to be licensed to third parties and therefore we will establish a common IP licensing framework, where each partner can license each other's IP and included it in their own offerings, under preferential conditions.
Network and system activity logs module	Tasks: 4.4, 5.4 Tools: Network and forensic analysis security module	Product & Service	NTUA, PDM	<p>As a national academic institute NTUA is not allowed to sell any of the developed modules of iTrust6G in any market. Instead, it will:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inspire academic research including publications, undergraduate theses, and PhD programs. Consulting services one similar aspects for other European projects and submitting new proposals. Licensed for stand- alone solution or for integration into cybersecurity applications <p>PDM will seek a licensing agreement from NTUA to incorporate any development in this module into our current portfolio of Forensics Analysis tools.</p>
Policy enforcement and explainability mechanisms	PDP based on policies directly derived from intent. Decision evidence are combined with intent roll-back to explain decisions to users and admins	Product focused on service enhancement	TID, UC3M	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate this features in the 5TONIC testbed. Provide an open-source reference implementation. Explore opportunities for commercial differentiation by technology providers via licensing.

7.8 Individual exploitation plans and activities

This section provides the current results achieved within the individual exploitation plan of each partner.

7.8.1 Gigasys Solutions (GIGASYS)

Gigasys Solutions (GIGASYS) is an SME on wireless consultancy and project management in collaborative R&D in ICT. GIGASYS will use selected iTrust6G results for strengthening its consulting competency and to deliver value to its clients in the telecommunications industry across Europe. The exploitation of iTrust6G results by GIGASYS follows a three-step process:

- i) Identification of exploitable project results on a continuous basis by GIGASYS' key personnel;
- ii) Generation of White Papers and other information items based on the identified exploitable project results;

- iii) Value creation for clients through discussions, follow-up research and innovation as well as consulting on emerging networks, services, and applications related to the identified exploitable project results.

GIGASYS will advise its telco clients and partners via bi- and multi-lateral exchanges, targeted workshops, and community-internal White Papers. Furthermore, GIGASYS will use iTrust6G results to advise its clients on opportunities and risks arising from iTrust6G results and the impact they may have.

7.8.2 i2CAT Foundation (I2CAT)

i2CAT Foundation is a non-profit technology centre that promotes R&D and innovation activities in the field of Information and Communication Technologies and the Future Internet. The strategic objectives of i2CAT are:

- to integrate research, development and innovation;
- to foster co-creation using the Quadruple Helix model
- to develop activities within hybrid international and regional framework.

About technological transfer, i2CAT's exploitation plans are focused on the different development activities in iTrust6G by making improvements on the different modules, which are and will be part of the 5G assets catalogue of i2CAT. These enhancements and new features touch on several areas described next.

One of the assets from i2CAT, specifically, the countermeasure recommender, will be extended to develop and implemented additional features related to security decision-making process. This will cover the planning of security measures, the unification of security tools interfacing and the enforcement of security policy across disparate solution. These improvements will capitalise on the line of work related to security programmability to increase (i) the visibility over these security tools, contributing to iTrust6G's AI-driven security orchestration and facilitating cyber-threat intelligence generation and more precise trust assessment (ii) by permitting in-depth actuation of security measures, providing extensive material to formulate explanation on the security decision and enforcement to iTrust6G future customers.

i2CAT bolsters its IPR portfolio in accordance with a long-term plan to attract capital investments and even create new start-up companies.

For research, the acquired know-how has permitted to address new research topics related to system security, security-by-design of distributed systems, and trustworthy networking. Initial project results have been incorporated into several project proposals under evaluation of EC and SNS.

For consultancy, i2CAT proposes R&D services in Cybersecurity to public bodies in Catalonia and private organizations at a national and European level. The enhancement of i2CAT's knowledge and competence in the field of 6G network security will facilitate industrial collaborations and attract more research funding for developing innovative solutions (i2CAT assets), particularly the Countermeasure Recommender on incident response topics. However, up to the date of publication of this document, no consultancy service has involved iTrust6G results.

7.8.3 Telefonica (TID)

TID is specially interested in incorporating results in the areas of Zero-Trust, intent-based service consumption and management, evidence-based service enhancements, and explainability support to 5G-Advanced and 6G infrastructures, and in generalizing these results to any network-based service in the edge-network-cloud continuum. TID intends to apply these results via:

- Incorporating iTrust6G results in relevant standards and industry fora, making sure the operators' top-tier requirements are captured and prioritized in these fora, with the objective to steer architecture evolution and advanced security solutions there, especially in what regards to frictionless interaction between operator assets and third-party applications. The main targets are related to automation standards (ETSI ZSM, 3GPP SA5 and IETF OPS Area), security aspects (3GPP SA3, ETSI SAI and IETF Security Area) and data solutions (especially the recently created TC DATA, and activities in IETF ART and OPS areas)
- Considering the extension of management procedures (such as the Integration Fabric defined by ETSI ZSM) and third-party exposure interfaces (such as Linux Foundation's CAMARA and GSMA's Open Gateway) to incorporate the principles, protocols and tooling developed in the project, and promoting their use by third-party app developers.
- Demonstrating the features of iTrust6G solutions at the 5TONIC environment to Telefonica's B2B units, which will be using them to outline the appropriate go-to-market strategy for the commercial roll-out of these capabilities.

7.8.4 Lenovo (LEN)

Lenovo (LEN) is a multinational technology company specializing in designing, manufacturing, and marketing consumer electronics, personal computers, software, servers, converged and hyperconverged infrastructure solutions, and related services. In iTrust6G, LEN has contributed to exploitation of the results in the following ways:

- **For Market & Product Development:** Actively contributed to 3GPP SA3 WG for contributions and new study item proposals on Telecom Network Zero Trust Security to drive the standardization in line with the project activities (detailed in Chapter 6). Furthermore, disseminated new security concepts like T5.5 Secure Service Orchestration, schemes, and tools that the project developed through project blog post.
- **For Research and Education:** Associated the project with Ph.D. research and exploited the results for new security and privacy services including peer reviewed paper submission in conferences. The constructive collaboration within the project is a strong basis for future collaborative partnerships and projects with other Business Units inside Lenovo specially for AI Research and Security.

7.8.5 PDMFC (PDM)

PDM, a research-intensive SME with a strong history of developing advanced security tools and successful spinoff ventures, is strategically positioned to leverage its expertise and collaborative partnerships to drive innovation and market penetration in telecommunications and mobility solutions. Here's an initial exploitation plan:

1. Leveraging Existing Security Portfolio:
 - Identity and Access Management for B2B services, commercial agreement signed by Vodafone, to provide new security services to their customers.
 - Digital Forensics (POC being evaluated by LEAs third party consultants in Portugal), for automated crypto signing in data acquisition, and strong guarantee for evidence custody chain.
 - Metadon SIEM ongoing POC with Hospital Espirito Santo in Portugal. To secure their network services.
 - IDPS (currently being evaluated by mobile operators in the national 5G testbed).

- Extend these tools to the field of next-generation network technologies (high-volume heavily distributed, think millions of EPS per tenant)
2. Utilization of Vodafone Portugal (PT) Testbed:
 - PDM is working with Vodafone Portugal (PT) to ensure the feasibility of a POC for deploying the **iTrust6G** technologies within Vodafone PT's network will validate scalability, interoperability, and reliability, providing valuable insights for further refinement and optimization.
 3. Integration within PDM Ecosystem:
 - Collaboration among the companies within the PDM ecosystem will facilitate seamless integration and customization of security and AI technologies across diverse product offerings and market segments.
 - PDM is working closely with its affiliates to tailor solutions to meet specific requirements and use cases, maximizing relevance and impact across the ecosystem.
 4. Utilization of EU Services for Visibility:
 - PDM will leverage EU-provided services such as the Innovation Radar and the Horizon Results Booster to enhance visibility and market penetration.
 - Active engagement with these platforms will showcase technological advancements, attracting potential partners, investors, and customers to accelerate commercialization and adoption.

In summary, PDM's initial exploitation plan focuses on leveraging its research expertise, strategic partnerships, and collaborative synergies to establish a strong foothold in telecommunications and mobility solutions. Through technology integration, market validation, and targeted deployment strategies, PDM aims to unlock new opportunities and drive sustained growth and innovation in the evolving digital landscape.

7.8.6 Adrestia (ADR)

Adrestia R&D (ADR) is responsible for creating two software services, defining a new set of cybersecurity referential regarding the evaluation of trust in the design of operated resources, and coordinating and integrating the **iTrust6G** platform in the pilot scenarios.

Moreover, since the project is currently in a development stage, adjustments will be made to the exploitation plan to comply with the needs of the **iTrust6G** platform.

During the first 16 months of the project, ADR proceeded with the development of the software services and the definition of a new set of cybersecurity referential. There are no deviations from the original planning. Regarding exploitation, ADR will incorporate one of the in-development software services (namely, the threat detection and classification service) within one of its upcoming product-release as a new feature. The incorporation of the other service is also in planning, but not yet completely merged. Regarding the upcoming exploitation plan, an exploitation strategy is finalized and includes both commercial and non-commercial means. Commercial exploitation will involve entering into licensing agreements with clients and offering the developed solutions as part of ADR's product line. Non-commercial exploitation will focus on collaborations with academic institutions, which will enable continued research, development, and refinement of the technologies produced under **iTrust6G**.

7.8.7 National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)

As a public institution of higher education NTUA is a non-profit organisation that will not perform commercial exploitation of the project's results. Nevertheless, NTUA will have significant benefits to reap from the

project results that we outline below. The project's team will incorporate material and research results of the project in related courses in the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, perform seminars and further train undergraduate students as part of their final year projects. Postgraduate students attending the MSc in Techno-economic students will also benefit from similar inclusion of the project's results in courses, projects, and seminars. Additionally, 6 theses, 5 from undergraduate students and 1 from a post graduate student, are actively being carried out, which also helps broaden the overall research spectrum of the institution.

PhD theses will also be drawn out based either directly or indirectly from the project's results in the areas of NTUA's scientific contributions to the project, from members of the project's team, as well as new PhD candidates. These candidates along with the senior researchers and faculty members intend to further their expertise in the fields of networking and future 6g networks, digital and network forensics, federated learning, artificial intelligence in general, standardisation and implementation of standards. This expertise will be used to publish research papers, attend, and present work in conferences, and allow the participation of NTUA in other closely or loosely related research projects.

7.8.8 Politecnico di Torino (POLITO)

POLITO is a public university, hence a non-profit organization. As such, its main exploitation plan is the reuse of projects' results in its education, research, and consultancy activities.

For education, some results of iTrust6G have already been used in the "Advanced Information Systems Security" MSc course for the Cybersecurity Engineering program. Additionally, four PhD students have a research subject connected to iTrust6G and several theses have been executed with a topic related to iTrust6G.

For research, the initial project's results have been used in further project proposals, currently under evaluation by the EC.

For consultancy, POLITO acts often as an advisor for public administrations and private companies for cybersecurity topics. Given the current emphasis on adoption of 5G/6G technologies, the knowledge and results obtained in iTrust6G will improve the capacity of POLITO to win consultancy contracts and to successfully perform them. However, no consultancy task on these subjects has been requested in the first 15 months of the project.

7.9 Business canvas

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management tool designed to help entrepreneurs and organizations visually map, design, and analyse their business models on a single page. Developed by Alexander Osterwalder, the canvas breaks down a business into nine fundamental building blocks, making it easier to understand and communicate how a company creates and captures value [14].

The main features of business canvas are derived from the visual aspect, where a one-page format canvas provides a high-level view of a business model. It aims to replace a lengthy business plan with a concise alternative that is much easier to understand and grasp. This leads to strategic clarity that helps teams and stakeholder quickly point out strengths and weaknesses as well as opportunities. It has become widely used and adopted by both startups and established organizations.

7.9.1 Business canvas template

Figure 7-1 Business Canvas Template

The template in Figure 7-1 provides 9 building blocks, from top left to bottom right they are:

1. Key Partners – Identification of the network of suppliers and partners that help the business model work.
2. Key Activities – Description of the most relevant things a project must do to make its business model successful.
3. Key Resources – List of the important assets required for the business model.
4. Value Propositions – Description of the bundle of products and services that create value for a specific customer segment.
5. Customer Relationships – Explains the types of relationships a project must establish with a specific customer segment.
6. Customer Segments – Description of the different groups of people or organizations a project aims to reach and serve.
7. Channels – Outline how a project communicates and reaches its customer segments to deliver the value proposition.
8. Cost Structure – Summary of costs involved in the operating model.
9. Revenue Streams: Represents the cash a project generates from each customer segment.

7.9.2 iTrust6G instance

In this section we present the instantiation of the business canvas template to the iTrust6G project in Figure 7-2.

Figure 7-2 Business Canvas iTrust6G instance

Key Partners

The iTrust6G project involves a consortium of diverse partners crucial for its success:

- **Research Institutes:** Such as i2CAT, providing specialized research capabilities;
- **Industry Leaders:** Including Telefónica and Lenovo, bringing industry perspective and infrastructure;
- **Academic Institutions:** NTUA and POLITO contribute academic research and expertise;
- **SMEs:** Gigasys, PDMFC, and Adrestia offer specialized skills and solutions.

Key Activities

The core activities undertaken by the iTrust6G project are centred around developing and validating its security framework:

- Development of AI-driven security solutions;
- Implementation of a Zero-Trust Architecture (ZTA) adapted for 6G networks;
- Research and development in threat intelligence gathering and detection;
- Orchestration of security policies across domains;
- Integration of the developed solutions with 6G infrastructure components;
- Validation of the framework and its components through defined use cases and testbeds.

Key Resources

iTrust6G relies on several key resources:

- **Expertise and Algorithms:** Primarily in AI and ML applied to cybersecurity

- **Platforms:** Security orchestration platforms form a core part of the technical infrastructure
- **Infrastructure:** Test facilities and infrastructure, such as the 5TONIC Lab, are essential for validation
- **Personnel:** Dedicated research and development teams from partner organizations
- **Intellectual Property (IP):** The project's IP portfolio generated through research
- **Hardware:** Hardware acceleration platforms may be used for specific functions like ML Accelerators and TEEs

Value Propositions

iTrust6G aims to deliver significant value primarily focused on enhancing security and trust in future 6G networks, propositions include:

- Enhanced security specifically tailored for 6G network environments
- Intelligent and automated trust management mechanisms
- Automated detection of cyber threats
- Solutions that preserve privacy during security operations
- Security isolation capabilities for multi-tenant environments
- Potential for reduced operational costs through automation
- Alignment with and support for compliance with relevant EU regulations (e.g., NIS2)

Customer Relationships

The project engages with its stakeholders and potential adopters through various relationship types:

- **Technical Consultancy:** Providing expert advice based on project findings
- **Research Partnerships:** Collaborating with other research entities and projects
- **Knowledge Transfer:** Sharing findings through publications, workshops, and demonstrations
- **Training Programs:** Potentially offering training on the developed technologies
- **Support Services:** Providing support for implemented solutions
- **Collaborative Development:** Working jointly with stakeholders on specific solutions or use cases

Customer Segments

The primary target groups and beneficiaries of the iTrust6G project results are diverse stakeholders within the telecommunications and related ecosystems:

- **Telecom Operators:** Who will manage and operate future 6G networks
- **Cloud Service Providers:** Offering infrastructure for network functions
- **IoT Solution Providers:** Developing applications reliant on 6G connectivity
- **Industrial Manufacturers:** Utilizing 6G for Industry 4.0 applications
- **Critical Infrastructure Operators:** Relying on secure and resilient communication networks
- **Security Service Providers:** Offering security solutions integrated with 6G

Channels

iTrust6G utilizes multiple channels to reach its customer segments and disseminate results through:

iTrust6G [SNS-JU-101139198]

- **Direct Engagement:** Potentially direct sales or licensing, particularly targeting telecom operators
- **Research Publications:** Disseminating findings through scientific papers and journals
- **Industry Conferences:** Presenting results and demonstrating solutions at relevant events
- **Standardization Contributions:** Influencing future standards through contributions to bodies like ETSI
- **Open-Source Releases:** Making software components publicly available
- **Technical Demonstrations:** Showcasing capabilities in test environments like 5TONIC

Cost Structure

The main costs associated with the iTrust6G project include:

- **R&D Investments:** Core funding for research and development activities
- **Personnel Costs:** Salaries and related costs for researchers and developers
- **Infrastructure and Testing:** Costs associated with testbeds, hardware, and software for development and validation
- **IP Protection:** Costs related to patents and intellectual property management
- **Marketing and Dissemination:** Expenses for publications, conference attendance, website, and promotional materials
- **Standardization Activities:** Costs associated with participating in standardization bodies

Revenue Streams

While primarily a research and innovation project, potential revenue or value-generation streams identified include:

- **Technology Licensing:** Licensing the developed technologies and IP to interested parties
- **Consulting Services:** Offering expertise and consulting based on project outcomes
- **Implementation Support:** Providing support for the adoption and implementation of iTrust6G solutions
- **Training and Certification:** Offering training programs and potentially certifications related to the framework
- **Research Funding:** Securing follow-on research grants or funding based on project success
- **Patent Royalties:** Generating income from patented inventions

8 Summary and Conclusions

This document, iTrust6G D7.2, describes the activities performed by the project in its first 16 months on communication and dissemination of the results, contributions to standardisation activities, individual and joint exploitation plans, and the liaisons with other organisations.

Results are mostly satisfactory and in line with expectations. A joint analysis will be conducted by all partners to identify areas that require more effort, and plans will be updated correspondingly.

A final report on the activities reported in this document will be prepared and submitted at the end of the project (i.e. month 30) to produce the iTrust6G D7.3 “Final Report on Dissemination, Impact and Exploitation of the Results”.

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